

SYSTEMIC SYNUCLEIN SAMPLING STUDY (S4) DATA DICTIONARY

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Introductions & Instructions

Cross-sectional Clinical, Slide Imaging, and Biologics Data

The Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study (S4) aimed to investigate the levels and distribution of the protein alpha-synuclein and other biomarkers in Parkinson’s disease. S4 data is a rich data set facilitating discovery, validation, and reproducibility in Parkinson’s disease research. The data set was generated through cross-sectional clinical measurements (health and medical history questionnaires administered by a clinic practitioner), brain imaging, and analysis of assays performed on biofluids and tissues. S4 is a cross-sectional study *without longitudinal follow-up*, meaning that study activities could be completed over a 16-week time period as described in the [S4 Clinical Study Protocol](#). As part of the testing battery, biological samples including DNA, RNA, CSF, plasma, serum, whole blood, saliva, skin, colon tissue, and submandibular gland tissue were collected from participants. These samples are distributed to academic laboratories and industry groups on an ongoing basis for analysis and the resultant data are returned and are distributed to the public when they become available. As new studies are released, a new version of this data dictionary will be posted in the below table:

Version	Date	Author	Version Notes
1.1	4/12/2023	Dave Alonso	Updated to describe additional SAA biologics and genotyping data
1.0	12/05/2022	Dave Alonso	Initial version describing cross-sectional clinical and slide imaging data

Qualified researchers can access S4 data at <https://zenodo.org/record/7431680#.ZDWSonbMK5d>.

It is recommended that the S4 protocol and the following four publications be reviewed in conjunction with this data dictionary:

1. *Visanji NP, Mollenhauer B, Beach TG, Adler CH, Coffey CS, Kopil CM, Dave KD, Foroud T, Chahine L, Jennings D; Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study (S4). The Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study: toward a biomarker for Parkinson's disease. Biomark Med. 2017*

- Apr;11(4):359-368. doi: 10.2217/bmm-2016-0366. Epub 2017 Mar 29. PMID: 28353371. ([link](#))
2. Beach TG, Serrano GE, Kremer T, Canamero M, Dziadek S, Sade H, Derkinderen P, Corbillé AG, Letournel F, Munoz DG, White CL 3rd, Schneider J, Crary JF, Sue LI, Adler CH, Glass MJ, Intorcía AJ, Walker JE, Foroud T, Coffey CS, Ecklund D, Riss H, Goßmann J, König F, Kopil CM, Arnedo V, Riley L, Linder C, Dave KD, Jennings D, Seibyl J, Mollenhauer B, Chahine L; Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study (S4). Immunohistochemical Method and Histopathology Judging for the Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study (S4). *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. 2018 Sep 1;77(9):793-802. ([link](#))
 3. Chahine LM, Beach TG, Seedorff N, Caspell-Garcia C, Coffey CS, Brumm M, Adler CH, Serrano GE, Linder C, Mosovsky S, Foroud T, Riss H, Ecklund D, Seibyl J, Jennings D, Arnedo V, Riley L, Dave KD, Mollenhauer B; Systemic Synuclein Sampling study. Feasibility and Safety of Multicenter Tissue and Biofluid Sampling for α -Synuclein in Parkinson's Disease: The Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study (S4). *J Parkinsons Dis*. 2018;8(4):517-527. ([link](#))
 4. Chahine LM, Beach TG, Brumm MC, Adler CH, Coffey CS, Mosovsky S, Caspell-Garcia C, Serrano GE, Munoz DG, White CL 3rd, Crary JF, Jennings D, Taylor P, Foroud T, Arnedo V, Kopil CM, Riley L, Dave KD, Mollenhauer B; Systemic Synuclein Sampling Study. In vivo distribution of α -synuclein in multiple tissues and biofluids in Parkinson disease. *Neurology*. 2020 Sep. 1;95(9):e1267-e1284 ([link](#))

USING S4 DATA

Clinical Data Structure and Unique Identifier

The S4 clinical data set is shared in **wide format**: one row/observation contains information for *one clinical measurement for one participant*. That means that each participant *may* have multiple rows in a table, if the clinical measurement allowed for entry of more than one observation at time of collection. Each table contains all the responses for a given clinical measurement.

The data set contains a **Unique Identifier** for participants, a set of **Variables**, and a set of **Temporal Variables** for certain clinical measurements, where observation date was collected. We provide the definitions below.

Field	Name	Definition
Unique Identifier	SubjectID	4-digit integer which contains a unique, de-identified, number assigned to participants. Ex: '3864'.
Variables	Ex: RigidityNeckOff, SagittalSide	Individual variable definitions are provided in this data dictionary by table. Most variables are direct and raw responses from either clinical staff or participants reported from case report forms (CRFs). Others are derived variables, which have undergone a transformation either to protect confidentiality or to render them usable for analysis. When this is the case, it is indicated in the data dictionary.

Temporal Variables	Ex: VisitDTDays, CollectionDTDays, AssessmentDTDays, etc.	For a given clinical measurement (where observation date was collected), the number of days that have elapsed since a participant has consented to the study. Not all tables have an associated temporal variable; for tables that do, it is called out in the individual table descriptions below. These variables can be used to determine the number of days between events.
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Combining Multiple S4 Tables (Clinical Data)

The **Unique Identifier (SubjectID)** and **Temporal Variables** are the key variables that will enable you to combine and transform S4 data to meet your research needs. If you are interested in conducting cross-sectional analyses (e.g., one record per participant), you can use **SubjectID** to identify and combine all tables for a single participant. Bear in mind, an individual may have multiple records in a single table, so you may wish to consider whether you need data which was collected in a single time point, or alternatively whether you wish to specify a specific time of responses. Either approach can be accomplished by using the **Temporal Variable** associated with that specific clinical measurement.

Slide Imaging Data Format, Naming Convention, and Linking to Clinical Data

The S4 slide imaging data were generated as follows. Each biopsy sample (colon, skin, submandibular) was obtained and placed in cassettes, subsequently sliced onto slides, and histological stains were applied. Digital images of the stained slides were then obtained. Multiple biopsy fragments were obtained for each participant for each tissue type, and therefore there are multiple cassettes per subject, and for each tissue type. These images are available as two distinct, interrelated data sets:

1. **H&E slide images**
2. **Targos slide images**, immunostained for α -syn pathology with the 5C12 antibody by a central lab (Targos Molecular Pathology GmbH) and digitally scanned at 40x magnification.

A subset of **H&E slide images** has corresponding **Targos slide images** that were derived from the same tissue sample; meaning that there are instances where **H&E slide images** do not have an associated **Targos slide imaging** file.

The **H&E slide images** are shared in Tag Image File Format (.tif) and can be downloaded as a compressed .zip file titled '*H_E_Images.zip*'. The file is organized in the following hierarchy:

H_E_Images → *<Tissue type>*, where:

- **Tissue type** is the type of tissue collected (Colon, Skin, or Submandibular Gland).

Each sub-folder contains a set of .tif files associated with the tissue type specified in the parent folders with the following naming convention:

‘Subj <Alternate ID> cassette <Cassette #> slide [Sequential #].tif’, where:

- **Alternate ID** is a blinded, alternative participant ID
- **Cassette #** is an identifier for the tissue cassette used to capture a specimen
- **Sequential #** is the position of a given slice of tissue within a specimen

Note: These files can be linked to the clinical data via **SubjectID** by way of the ‘S4 Linkage File.xlsx’.

Name	Date	Type	Size
Subj 2025 cassette 221 slide 21	1/18/2017 11:35 AM	TIF File	2,273 KB
Subj 2025 cassette 221 slide 42	1/18/2017 11:35 AM	TIF File	2,273 KB
Subj 2025 cassette 221 slide 63	1/18/2017 11:35 AM	TIF File	2,273 KB
Subj 2025 cassette 221 slide 84	1/18/2017 11:35 AM	TIF File	2,273 KB

Example (screenshot above): File ‘Subj 2025 cassette 221 slide 21.tif’ corresponds to **SubjectID** 3082 (Alternate ID = 2025), is derived from a colon biopsy sample from cassette S4-221, sequence 21.

The **Targos slide images** consist of the following two file types: ScanScope Virtual Slide (.svs) and XML Document (.xml). The .xml files contain requisite text data that corresponds to each slide image, and therefore should not be unpaired. From each sample in a cassette, 3 slide images are available. These slide images can be downloaded as 17 separate compressed .zip files. For user convenience files are organized by batch, run number, and processing date. Batches 11 and 12 were split into multiple parts due to their file size. Batch 3 Run 20 and Batch 6 Run 45 failed and are therefore excluded from the final dataset. The files are organized in the following hierarchy:

Targos_Images → <Batch #>.zip, where:

- **Batch #** is the batch number.

Each sub-folder contains a set of .svs and .xml files associated with the batch and run numbers specified in the parent folder. Each slide is identified by a Cassette # and *uniquely* identified by

a Sequential # (the glass slide number) and Targos Sample #. Files have been named with the following convention:

'[Cassette #]_[Sequential #]_[Targos Sample #]_[Structure]', where:

- **Cassette #** is an identifier for the tissue cassette used to capture a specimen
- **Sequential #** is the position of a given slice of tissue within a specimen
- **Structure** is the tissue type (e.g., colon, skin, submandibular)

Note: These files can be linked to the clinical data via **SubjectID** by way of the 'S4 Linkage File.xlsx'.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
S4-204_44_628948_COLON	5/6/2021 10:11 PM	SVS File	143,606 KB
S4-204_44_628948_COLON	5/6/2021 10:08 PM	Microsoft Edge H...	12 KB
S4-204_54_628950_COLON	5/6/2021 9:27 PM	SVS File	119,424 KB
S4-204_54_628950_COLON	5/6/2021 9:39 PM	Microsoft Edge H...	11 KB

Example (screenshot above): Files 'S4-204_44_628948_COLON.svs' and 'S4-204_44_628948_COLON.xml' correspond to **SubjectID** 3941 (Alternate ID = 2856), is derived from a colon biopsy sample from cassette S4-204, sequence 44.

The information contained in the .xml files are as follows:

Rules for the Annotation of Tissue Fragments on Digital Images

The XML file contains information for numbering the different sections of tissue on a given slide: the numbering of tissue fragments that are mounted on the study slides slide. They represent respective annotations electronically on digital images of the slides. A separate small data file that carries the annotation information is included with the digital image files.

Annotation of fragments occurred according to the following rules:

Biopsy 1 is defined as the only biopsy or that closest to the slide label, or above the other biopsy on the slide.

Biopsy 2 is defined as the biopsy farther from the slide label or below the other biopsy.

Biopsy 3 is defined as the biopsy farthest from the slide label or above the second biopsy. (Biopsy #3 is mainly expected for submandibular gland tissue)

When a biopsy appears to have split into two, three or more fragments, the fragments are circled together as groups, with **up to two groups for skin and colon sections**, and **up to three**

groups for submandibular gland sections. Alternatively, slides may have only on tissue fragment or group of fragments.

Each slide may contain up to 3 fragments, as annotated on the digital image, but could contain 2 (or even 1).

Sample slide with only two biopsies (shown below):

For Reference: Slide Label Info (shown below):

α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) Data

Seed amplification assay (SAA) testing on cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and submandibular gland (SMG) samples were performed as described in the following publication:

- L.M. Chahine, T.G. Beach, C.H. Adler, M. Hepker, A. Kanthasamy, S. Appel, S. Pritzkow, M. Pinho, S. Mosovsky, G.E. Serrano, C. Coffey, M.C. Brumm, L.M.A. Oliveira, J. Eberling, B. Mollenhauer, Central and peripheral α -synuclein in Parkinson disease detected by seed amplification assay, *Ann Clin Transl Neurol* (2023) ([link](#))

These data are shared in .csv format and can be downloaded as a file titled '*Analysis_SAA.csv*'. Individual variables are described below in the **Analysis of CSF and SMG samples using alpha-synuclein SAA test (Analysis_SAA)** table. These files can be linked to the other data modalities via **SubjectID**.

Genotyping Data

Genotyping data was generated by the Global Parkinson's Genetic Program (GP2) using whole blood samples collected during the S4 study. These data are available via official GP2 releases ([here](#)). If you have any questions about the QC process or the ancestry prediction pipeline, refer to the [GenoTools GitHub](#).

Modified Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living (ADL)

Table Description: Modified Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from study participants who endorse a diagnosis of Parkinson's disease via the 'Form 10 – Modified Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
ADL	Numeric	Select the description below that best describes the participant's condition	0	0% Vegetative functions such as swallowing, bladder, and bowel functions are not functioning. Bedridden.	
			10	10% Totally dependent, helpless. Complete invalid.	
			20	20% Nothing alone. Can be a slight help with some chores. Severe invalid.	
			30	30% With effort, now and then does a few chores alone or begins alone. Much help needed.	
			40	40% Very dependent. Can assist with all chores but few alone.	
			50	50% More dependent. Help with half, slower, etc. Difficulty with everything.	
			60	60% Some dependency. Can do most chores, but exceedingly slowly and with much effort. Errors; some impossible.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			70	70% Not completely independent. More difficulty with some chores. Three to four times as long in some. Must spend a large part of the day with chores.	
			80	80% Completely independent in most chores. Takes twice as long. Conscious of difficulty and slowness.	
			90	90% Completely independent. Able to do all chores with some degree of slowness, difficulty and impairment. Might take twice as long. Beginning to be aware of difficulty.	
			100	100% Completely independent. Able to do all chores without slowness, difficulty or impairment. Essentially normal. Unaware of any difficulty.	

Adverse Event List (AEList)

Table Description: Adverse Event List

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 25 – Adverse Event' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
PreExist	Numeric	Is this an exacerbation of a pre-existing condition (existing prior to enrollment)?	0	No	These variables are collected with the prompt (check all that apply).
			1	Yes	
OutcomeDeath	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Death	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeLifeThreat	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Life Threatening	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeDisability	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Disability	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeCongenital	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Congenital Anomaly	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeIntervention	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Required Intervention to Prevent Permanent Impairment/Damage	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeMedicalEvent	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – Important Medical Events as Determined by the Site PI or Designee	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
OutcomeNone	Numeric	Attributes of Adverse Event – None of the Above (non-serious AE)	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
Intensity	Numeric	Intensity: NOTE: Please follow CTCAE 4 Guidelines	1	Mild/Grade I	
			2	Moderate/Grade II	
			3	Severe/Grade III	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			4	Life Threatening/Grade IV	
			5	Death/Grade V	
RelatedToStudy	Numeric	Related to study procedure:	1	Unrelated	
			2	Unlikely Related	
			3	Possibly Related	
			4	Probably Related	
			5	Definitely Related	
RelatedProcedure	Numeric	Which study procedure is this (S)AE related to?	1	Skin Biopsy	
			2	Colon Biopsy	
			3	Submandibular Gland Biopsy	
			4	Lumbar Puncture	
			5	Blood Collected	
			6	DATScan	
			7	Other	
Terminated	Numeric	Did this event result in study termination?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Serious	Numeric	Is the adverse event a Serious Adverse Event (SAE)?	1	No, non-serious	For SAEs only – this variable was not populated for non-serious adverse events
			2	Yes, serious	
Related	Numeric	Is the event related to the study intervention?	1	Definite	For SAEs only – clinical staff respond to this if they answer ‘Yes’ to the question ‘Is the adverse event a Serious Adverse Event (SAE)?’
			2	Probable	
			3	Possible	
			4	Unlikely	
			5	Unrelated	
Expected	Numeric	Is the event expected?	1	Unexpected	For SAEs only – clinical staff respond to this if they answer ‘Yes’ to the question ‘Is the adverse event a Serious Adverse Event (SAE)?’
			2	Expected	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
AdverseEventDTDays	Numeric	Date of Adverse Event (AE) [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
DeathDTDays	Numeric	Death Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes and is blank for non-serious adverse events
PT_Name	Text	Preferred Term (MedDRA) [Derived]	-	-	Aeterm MedDRA coded to preferred term
SOC_Name	Text	System Organ Class (MedDRA) [Derived]	-	-	Aeterm MedDRA coded to system organ class

Analysis of CSF and SMG samples using alpha-synuclein SAA test (Analysis_SAA)

Table Description: Analysis of CSF and SMG samples using alpha-synuclein SAA test

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor by seed amplification assay (SAA) testing on cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and submandibular gland (SMG) samples.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
fmax_csf	Numeric	Maximal fluorescence (CSF)	-	-	This variable represents fluorescence in units of relative fluorescence units
t50_csf	Numeric	Time needed to reach 50% of maximum aggregation (CSF)	-	-	This variable represents time in units of hours
auc_csf	Numeric	Area under the curve (CSF)	-	-	
slope_csf	Numeric	Kinetics of elongation phase (CSF)	-	-	
cassette_smg_saa	Text	Cassette number (SMG)	-	-	
time_thresh_smg	Numeric	Time to threshold (SMG)	-	-	This variable represents time in units of hours
pct_max_rfu_smg	Numeric	Percent of maximal fluorescence (SMG)	-	-	
hill_slope_smg	Numeric	Kinetics of elongation phase (SMG)	-	-	

Blood Sampling (BloodSample)

Table Description: Blood Sampling

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 17 – Blood Sampling' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
LastFoodDTDays	Numeric	Date of last intake of food [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PDMedDTDays	Numeric	Date of most recent PD medication dosing [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PGFrozenDTDays	Numeric	Date samples were frozen (Paxgene) [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
LastFoodTM	Numeric	Time of last intake of food	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
FastingStatus	Numeric	Fasting status	1	Fasted (minimum of 8 hours)	
			2	Low Fat Diet	
			3	Not Fasted, No Low Fat Diet	
PDMed	Numeric	Is subject on medication for PD?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
PDMedTM	Numeric	Time of most recent PD medication dosing	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
PGCollectTM	Numeric	Time collection completed (Paxgene)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
PGFrozenTM	Numeric	Time samples were frozen (Paxgene)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
PGInversions	Numeric	Number of inversions (Paxgene)	-	-	
PGTubeNum	Numeric	Number of tubes (Paxgene)	-	-	
PGVolume	Numeric	Volume collected (Paxgene)	1	Complete	
			2	Incomplete	
PGStorageTemp	Numeric	Storage temperature if placed in freezer (Paxgene)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
PlasmaCollectTM	Numeric	Time collection completed (plasma)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
PlasmaCentrifugeTM	Numeric	Time of centrifugation (plasma)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
PlasmaCentrifugeRate	Numeric	Rate of centrifugation (plasma)	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of xg
PlasmaCentrifugeDuration	Numeric	Duration of centrifugation (plasma)	-	-	This variable represents rate in minutes
PlasmaCentrifugeTemp	Numeric	Temperature at which tube was centrifuged (plasma)	1	Room temperature	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
			2	Refrigerated	
PlasmaAliquotVol	Numeric	Total volume aliquotted after centrifuging (plasma)	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of mL
PlasmaAliquotNum	Numeric	Total number of aliquot tubes (plasma)	-	-	
PlasmaFrozenTM	Numeric	Time samples were frozen (plasma)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
PlasmaStorageTemp	Numeric	Storage temperature if placed in freezer (plasma)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
WholeBloodCollectTM	Numeric	Time collection completed (whole blood)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
WholeBloodVolume	Numeric	Volume collected (whole blood)	1	Complete tube	
			2	Incomplete tube	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
WholeBloodFrozenTM	Numeric	Time samples were frozen	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
WholeBloodFreezerTemp	Numeric	Freezer Storage temperature	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
WholeBloodCBCCloTM	Numeric	Time collection completed	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SerumCollectTM	Numeric	Time collection completed (serum)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SerumCentrifugeTM	Numeric	Time of centrifugation (serum)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SerumCentrifugeRate	Numeric	Rate of centrifugation (serum)	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of xg
SerumCentrifugeDuration	Numeric	Duration of centrifugation (serum)	-	-	This variable represents rate in minutes
SerumCentrifugeTemp	Numeric	Temperature at which tube was centrifuged (serum)	1	Room temperature	
			2	Refrigerated	
SerumAliquotVol	Numeric	Total volume aliquotted after centrifuging (serum)	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of mL
SerumAliquotNum	Numeric	Total number of aliquot tubes (serum)	-	-	
SerumFrozenTM	Numeric	Time samples were frozen (serum)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SerumStorageTemp	Numeric	Storage temperature if placed in freezer (serum)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
DNACollectTM	Numeric	Time collection completed (DNA)	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
DNATubeNum	Numeric	Number of tubes (DNA)	-	-	
DNAVolume	Numeric	Volume collected (DNA)	1	Complete tube	
			2	Incomplete tube	

Cervical Paravertebral Biopsy (CervicalBiopsy)

Table Description: Cervical Paravertebral Biopsy

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 20 – Skin Biopsy' CRF and is a child table to the 'SkinBiopsy' table.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CassetteNum	Text	Peach Cassette#	-	-	
SampleNum	Numeric	# of samples in cassette	-	-	
SagittalSide	Numeric	Side of biopsy	1	Right	
			2	Left	
Closure	Numeric	Closure	1	Steri-strip/bandaid	
			2	Suture	
BiopsyTM	Numeric	Time of biopsy	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
Fixative	Numeric	Type of fixative used	1	Formalin	
			2	Zamboni's	
FixativeTM	Numeric	Time sample placed in fixative	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
ChilledTM	Numeric	Time sample was chilled	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock

Clinical Safety Assessment (ClinSafe)

Table Description: Clinical Safety Assessment

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 14 – Clinical Safety Assessment' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Blood	Numeric	Abnormality Present?	0	No	This information is collected for the 'Blood drawn' clinical safety assessment
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
BloodSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
ECG	Numeric	Abnormality Present?	0	No	This information is collected for the 'ECG' clinical safety assessment
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
ECGSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
NotCollected	Text	Reason not collected	-	-	This is a free text variable that is populated when blood or ECG could not be collected
BloodDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality	-	-	This is a free text variable that is populated when abnormalities occurred while blood was drawn
ECGDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality	-	-	This is a free text variable that is populated when

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					abnormalities occurred while ECG was collected

Colon Biopsy (ColonBiopsy)

Table Description: Colon Biopsy

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 21 – Colon Biopsy' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PrePulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PreRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
PreSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
Sedation	Numeric	Sedation used for procedure?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Forceps	Numeric	Were radial jaw forceps used?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
CompletedTM	Numeric	Time for completion of biopsy procedure	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
FormulinTM	Numeric	Time sample placed in formalin	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
ChilledTM	Numeric	Time sample chilled	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SampleNum	Numeric	Number of tissue samples collected	-	-	
Cassette1	Text	Tan Cassette# (1)	-	-	
Cassette2	Text	Tan Cassette# (2)	-	-	
Cassette3	Text	Tan Cassette# (3)	-	-	
Cassette4	Text	Tan Cassette# (4)	-	-	
Cassette5	Text	Tan Cassette# (5)	-	-	
Cassette6	Text	Tan Cassette# (6)	-	-	
Cassette7	Text	Tan Cassette# (7)	-	-	
Cassette8	Text	Tan Cassette# (8)	-	-	
PostPulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PostRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
PostSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
SedationSpecify	Text	If yes please list sedative administered	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this as free text if they answer 'Yes' to the question 'Sedation used for procedure?'
OtherDeviceSpecify	Text	If another device was used please list	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this as free text if they answer

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					'No' to the question 'Were radial jaw forceps used?'
FormulinManu	Text	Formalin Manufacturer:	-	-	
FormulinLotNum	Numeric	Formalin Lot#:	-	-	
NotCollectedSpecify		If collection was not completed, why?	-	-	
Collected	Numeric	Colon biopsy collected:	1	Not Done	
			2	Collected	
			3	Partial Collection	
			4	Attempted, no collection	

Colon Pathology (ColonPath)

Table Description: Colon Pathology

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Colon Pathology' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
SlideNum	Numeric	Number of slides scored	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
BiopsyNum1	Numeric	Number of biopsies on slide 1	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
BiopsyNum2	Numeric	Number of biopsies on slide 2	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
BiopsyNum3	Numeric	Number of biopsies on slide 3	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
CassetteNum	Text	Cassette #	-	-	
SeqNum1	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 1)	-	-	
Compartment11	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density11	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment11_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density11_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	3	
Compartment12	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density12	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment12_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density12_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment13	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density13	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment13_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 3, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density13_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 3, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
SeqNum2	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 2)	-	-	
Compartment21	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density21	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment21_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density21_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment22	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density22	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment22_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density22_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment23s	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density23	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment23_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density23_sub	Numeric		0	0	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 3, submucosa)	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
SeqNum3	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 3)	-	-	
Compartment31	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density31	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 1, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment31_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density31_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 1, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment32	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density32	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 2, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment32_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density32_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 2, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment33	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Density33	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 3, mucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment33_sub	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 3, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
Density33_sub	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 3, submucosa)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	

Concomitant Medications (ConMeds)

Table Description: Concomitant Medications

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from study participants who *do not report a PD diagnosis* via the 'Form 24A – Concomitant Medications' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
EndDTDays	Numeric	End Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes and is blank for ongoing medication treatment
StartDTDays	Numeric	Start Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Dose	Numeric	Total (or average) Daily Dose	-	-	
DoseUnit	Numeric	Dose Units	1	g	This value represents dose units in grams
			2	mcg	This value represents dose units in micrograms
			3	mcL	This value represents dose units in microliters
			4	mg	This value represents dose units in milligrams
			5	mL	This value represents dose units in milliliters
			6	oz	This value represents dose units in ounces
			7	OTH	This value represents dose units as other, specified in

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					detail as a supporting free text variable (DoseUnitSpecify)
			8	UNK	This value represents unknown dose units
			9	NA	This value represents that dose units are not applicable
DoseFreq	Numeric	Dose Frequency	1	BID	This value represents dose frequency as twice daily
			2	TID	This value represents dose frequency as three times a day
			3	QID	This value represents dose frequency as four times a day
			4	q2h	This value represents dose frequency as every 2 hours
			5	q4h	This value represents dose frequency as every 4 hours
			6	q6h	This value represents dose frequency as every 6 hours
			7	q8h	This value represents dose frequency as every 8 hours
			8	QAM	This value represents dose frequency as one does in morning
			9	QPM	This value represents dose frequency as one dose in evening
			10	QD	This value represents dose frequency as once daily

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			11	QOD	This value represents dose frequency as alternating day (every other day)
			12	HS	This value represents dose frequency as at bedtime
			13	QWK	This value represents dose frequency as weekly
			14	QMT	This value represents dose frequency as monthly
			15	PRN	This value represents dose frequency as, as needed
			16	OTH	This value represents dose frequency as other, specified in detail as a supporting free text variable (DoseFreqSpecify)
			17	UNK	This value represents dose frequency as unknown
			18	NA	This value represents dose frequency as not applicable
			PRNFreq	Numeric	If PRN, Average Monthly Frequency
Route	Numeric	Route	1	IV	
			2	IM	
			3	PO	
			4	SC	
			5	PR	
			6	Sublingual	
			7	Inhaled	
			8	Topical	
			9	Other	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Ongoing	Numeric	Ongoing	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
AtcCode	Text	WHO Atc Code [Derived]	-	-	These variables are converted from the 'Treatment Name / Medication Name' column within the CRF to WHO standards (https://www.whooc.no/atc_ddd_index/)
GroupCode	Text	WHO group code [Derived]	-	-	
DrugNameCoded	Text	Name of medication [Derived]	-	-	
GroupText	Text	WHO group classification [Derived]	-	-	
DoseUnitSpecify	Text	Specify (dose unit)	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the dose unit is specified as 'OTH'
DoseFreqSpecify	Text	Specify (dose unit)	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the dose frequency is specified as 'OTH'

Concomitant Medications for PD (ConMedsPD)

Table Description: Concomitant Medications for PD

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from study participants who *report a PD diagnosis* via the 'Form 24B – Concomitant Medications for PD' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
EndDTDays	Numeric	End Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes and is blank for ongoing medication treatment
StartDTDays	Numeric	Start Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PillNum	Numeric	Number of pills per day (Combo drugs only)	-	-	
Dose	Numeric	Total (or average) Daily Dose	-	-	
DoseUnit	Numeric	Dose Units	1	g	This value represents dose units in grams
			2	mcg	This value represents dose units in micrograms
			3	mL	This value represents dose units in microliters
			4	mg	This value represents dose units in milligrams
			5	mL	This value represents dose units in milliliters
			6	oz	This value represents dose units in ounces

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			7	OTH	This value represents dose units as other, specified in detail as a supporting free text variable (DoseUnitSpecify)
			8	UNK	This value represents unknown dose units
			9	NA	This value represents that dose units are not applicable
DoseFreq	Numeric	Dose Frequency	1	BID	This value represents dose frequency as twice daily
			2	TID	This value represents dose frequency as three times a day
			3	QID	This value represents dose frequency as four times a day
			4	q2h	This value represents dose frequency as every 2 hours
			5	q4h	This value represents dose frequency as every 4 hours
			6	q6h	This value represents dose frequency as every 6 hours
			7	q8h	This value represents dose frequency as every 8 hours
			8	QAM	This value represents dose frequency as one does in morning
			9	QPM	This value represents dose frequency as one dose in evening

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			10	QD	This value represents dose frequency as once daily
			11	QOD	This value represents dose frequency as alternating day (every other day)
			12	HS	This value represents dose frequency as at bedtime
			13	QWK	This value represents dose frequency as weekly
			14	QMT	This value represents dose frequency as monthly
			15	PRN	This value represents dose frequency as, as needed
			16	OTH	This value represents dose frequency as other, specified in detail as a supporting free text variable (DoseFreqSpecify)
			17	UNK	This value represents dose frequency as unknown
			18	NA	This value represents dose frequency as not applicable
PRNFreq	Numeric	If PRN, Average Monthly Frequency	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the dose frequency is specified as 'PRN' (As needed)
Route	Numeric	Route	1	IV	
			2	IM	
			3	PO	
			4	SC	
			5	PR	
			6	Sublingual	
			7	Inhaled	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			8	Topical	
			9	Other	
Ongoing	Numeric	Ongoing	0	Not Checked	
			1	Checked	
AtcCode	Text	WHO Atc Code [Derived]	-	-	These variables are converted from the 'Treatment Name / Medication Name' column within the CRF to WHO standards (https://www.whooc.no/atc_ddd_index/)
GroupCode	Text	WHO group code [Derived]	-	-	
GroupText	Text	WHO group classification [Derived]	-	-	
DrugNameCoded	Text	Name of medication [Derived]	-	-	
DoseUnitSpecify	Text	Specify (dose unit)	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the dose unit is specified as 'OTH'
DoseFreqSpecify	Text	Specify (dose unit)	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the dose frequency is specified as 'OTH'

Demographics (Demographics)

Table Description: Demographics

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 2 – Demographics' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
BirthDTDays	Numeric	Date of Birth [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
CollectionDTDays	Numeric	Date of Collection [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Sex	Numeric		1	Male	
			2	Female	
Ethnicity	Numeric	Ethnicity (Select ONLY one)	1	Hispanic or Latino	
			2	Not Hispanic or Latino	
			3	Unknown	
			4	Not Reported	
RaceNR	Numeric	Race	1	Select all races with which the subject identifies	
			2	Unknown	
			3	Not reported	
RaceAI	Numeric	American Indian or Alaska Native	1	Not Checked	
			2	Checked	
RaceA	Numeric	Asian	1	Not Checked	
			2	Checked	
RaceAA	Numeric	Black or African-American	1	Not Checked	
			2	Checked	
RaceNH	Numeric	Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	1	Not Checked	
			2	Checked	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
RaceW	Numeric	White	1	Not Checked	
			2	Checked	
YearsOfEducation	Numeric	Years of education (0-30):	-	-	
PrimaryReferralSource	Numeric	Primary referral source:	0	Site Personnel	
			1	Fox Trial Finder	
			2	Family or Friend	
			3	Newspaper/TV/Radio	
			4	Online blog/news/social media	
			5	Educational event	
			6	MJFF Communication	
			7	Study Website	
			8	Primary Doctor or Medical Care Provider	
			9	Support group	
			10	PPMI study	
11	Biofind study				

Reason(s) for Ineligibility (healthy controls) (EligibilityHC_Ineligible)

Table Description: Reason(s) for Ineligibility (healthy controls)

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from study participants who *do not report a PD diagnosis*, during screening, via the 'Form 3B – Eligibility HC' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Age	Numeric	Male or female age 50 or older at the time of the screening visit.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
InfCons	Numeric	Ability to provide written informed consent in accordance with Good Clinical Practice (GCP), International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), and local regulations.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Willing	Numeric	Willing and able to comply with scheduled visits, required study procedures and laboratory tests.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
DiseaseHx	Numeric	Has a history of cancer (other than basal and squamous cell skin cancers), autoimmune disorder, liver disease, or other hematological disorder within the past 5 years.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Anticoagulants	Numeric	Current treatment with anticoagulants (e.g., Coumadin, heparin) that would preclude safe	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		completion of the lumbar puncture and tissue biopsy procedures.			
Antiplatelet	Numeric	Current treatment with more than one antiplatelet agent (Plavix or aspirin =325 mg/day).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Diabetes	Numeric	Has a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus requiring either an oral agent or insulin therapy.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Coagulopathy	Numeric	A bleeding diathesis, or clinically significant coagulopathy or thrombocytopenia.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Botox	Numeric	Have received botulinum toxin injections to the submandibular gland within the past year.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
LP	Numeric	Conditions that preclude safe performance of routine lumbar puncture, such as prohibitive lumbar spinal disease.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Sigmoid	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the flexible sigmoidoscopy procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable colonic tissue biopsies, including a prior colonoscopy with any significant finding (e.g. polyp with a positive finding,	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, inflammatory disease).			
Subman	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the submandibular gland procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable submandibular tissue biopsies, including any previous or active significant disease affecting the submandibular gland (e.g. inflammatory disease, infection, tumor).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Skin	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the skin punch biopsy procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable skin tissue biopsies, including any previous or active significant dermatological disease (e.g. previous biopsy with any of the following findings: inflammatory disease, scar tissue, psoriasis, keloid formation, skin cancer).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Investigator	Numeric	Any other medical or psychiatric condition or laboratory abnormality, which in the opinion of the	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		investigator would preclude participation.			
Drugs	Numeric	Use of investigational drugs or devices within 30 days prior to the screening visit.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
FamHxPD	Numeric	Has a family history of PD in any first-degree relative.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Neuro	Numeric	Has a significant neurological disorder (a neurodegenerative condition, clinically significant stroke, brain tumor, hydrocephalus, epilepsy, other neurodegenerative disorders, encephalitis, repeated head trauma, polyneuropathy).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
MoCA	Numeric	Has a Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) score < 26.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SleepREM	Numeric	Has a diagnosis of REM sleep behavior disorder.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Movement	Numeric	Has a primary dystonia, restless legs syndrome, essential tremor, or other movement disorder.	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Reason(s) for Ineligibility (PD) (EligibilityPD_Ineligible)

Table Description: Reason(s) for Ineligibility (PD)

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from study participants who *do not report a PD diagnosis*, during screening, via the 'Form 3A – Eligibility PD' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Age	Numeric	Male or female age 40 or older at the time of PD diagnosis.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
DxPD	Numeric	Clinical diagnosis of PD based on bradykinesia plus one of the following: rest tremor or rigidity.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
DaTSCAN	Numeric	DAT deficit at screening based on visual interpretation of DaTSCAN imaging.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
StageYN	Numeric	PD subjects will need to fall into one of the following stages: Early PD, Moderate PD, Advanced PD	0	No	
			1	Yes	
StagePD	Numeric	PD stage	1	Early untreated PD not requiring dopamine replacement medication (anticholinergics, MAO-B inhibitors and amantadine permitted), Hoehn and Yahr 1-2, < 2 years from diagnosis.	
			2	Moderate PD responsive and currently treated with dopamine replacement	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				therapy without evidence of motor fluctuations or dyskinesias.	
			3	Advanced PD with motor fluctuations or dyskinesias, > 5 years from diagnosis.	
InfCons	Numeric	Ability to provide written informed consent in accordance with Good Clinical Practice (GCP), International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), and local regulations.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Willing	Numeric	Willing and able to comply with scheduled visits, required study procedures and laboratory tests.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
DiseaseHx	Numeric	Has a history of cancer (other than basal and squamous cell skin cancers), autoimmune disorder, liver disease, or other hematological disorder within the past 5 years.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Anticoagulants	Numeric	Current treatment with anticoagulants (e.g., Coumadin, heparin) that would preclude safe completion of the lumbar puncture and tissue biopsy procedures.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Antiplatelet	Numeric	Current treatment with more than one antiplatelet	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		agent (Plavix or aspirin =325 mg/day).			
Diabetes	Numeric	Has a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus requiring either an oral agent or insulin therapy.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Coagulopathy	Numeric	A bleeding diathesis, or clinically significant coagulopathy or thrombocytopenia.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Botox	Numeric	Have received botulinum toxin injections to the submandibular gland within the past year.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
LP	Numeric	Conditions that preclude safe performance of routine lumbar puncture, such as prohibitive lumbar spinal disease.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Sigmoid	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the flexible sigmoidoscopy procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable colonic tissue biopsies, including a prior colonoscopy with any significant finding (e.g. polyp with a positive finding, ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, inflammatory disease).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Subman	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		submandibular gland procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable submandibular tissue biopsies, including any previous or active significant disease affecting the submandibular gland (e.g. inflammatory disease, infection, tumor).			
Skin	Numeric	Conditions that preclude the safe performance of the skin punch biopsy procedure or may interfere with obtaining evaluable skin tissue biopsies, including any previous or active significant dermatological disease (e.g. previous biopsy with any of the following findings: inflammatory disease, scar tissue, psoriasis, keloid formation, skin cancer).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Investigator	Numeric	Any other medical or psychiatric condition or laboratory abnormality, which in the opinion of the investigator would preclude participation.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Drugs	Numeric	Use of investigational drugs or devices within 30 days prior to the screening visit.	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Neuro	Numeric		0	No	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Has a significant neurological disorder (a neurodegenerative condition, clinically significant stroke, brain tumor, hydrocephalus, epilepsy, other neurodegenerative disorders, encephalitis, repeated head trauma, polyneuropathy).	1	Yes	
Autonomic	Numeric	Has significant autonomic dysfunction (symptomatic orthostasis, hypotension or urinary incontinence) suggestive of an atypical parkinsonismencephalitis, repeated head trauma, polyneuropathy).	0	No	
			1	Yes	
AtypicalPD	Numeric	Has atypical features of parkinsonism including but not limited to supranuclear gaze palsy, early recurrent falls, corticospinal track abnormalities, cerebellar abnormalities, significant cognitive dysfunction.	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Family History of PD (FamHxPD)

Table Description: Family History of PD

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 5 – Family History of PD' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CollectionDTDays	Numeric	Date of Collection [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
BIOMOMPD	Numeric	Biological mother:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
BIODADPD	Numeric	Biological father:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
MAGMOMPD	Numeric	Maternal grandmother:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
MAGDADPD	Numeric	Maternal grandfather:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
PAGMOMPD	Numeric	Paternal grandmother:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
PAGDADPD	Numeric	Paternal grandfather:	0	No	
			1	Yes	
KIDSNUM	Numeric	Biological children	-	-	
KIDSNUMPD	Numeric	Biological children (PD)	-	-	
FULSIB	Numeric	Full siblings	-	-	
FULSIBPD	Numeric	Full siblings (PD)	-	-	
HAFSIB	Numeric	Half siblings	-	-	
HAFSIBPD	Numeric	Half siblings (PD)	-	-	
MATAU	Numeric	Maternal aunts	-	-	
MATAUPD	Numeric	Maternal aunts (PD)	-	-	
MATUN	Numeric	Maternal uncles	-	-	
MATUNPD	Numeric	Maternal uncles (PD)	-	-	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
PATAU	Numeric	Paternal aunts	-	-	
PATAUPD	Numeric	Paternal aunts (PD)	-	-	
PATUN	Numeric	Paternal uncles	-	-	
PATUNPD	Numeric	Paternal uncles (PD)	-	-	
OtherRel	Numeric	Other	-	-	
OtherRelPD	Numeric	Other (PD)	-	-	

BioLegend data transfer (LabData_BioLegend)

Table Description: BioLegend data transfer

View Source Methods: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor by measuring total α -synuclein on CSF, saliva, whole blood, plasma, and serum using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) BioLegend α -Synuclein Immunoassay (BioLegend, San Diego, CA ,USA; Cat. No. 844101).

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Run_DateDays	Numeric	De-identified date sample analysis performed. [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Matrix	Text	Tissue type	CSF	-	
			Plasma	-	
			Saliva	-	
			Serum	-	
			Whole Blood	-	
Plate_number	Numeric	Plate #	1	-	
			2	-	
			3	-	
Position	Numeric	Location of sample on plate	Range (3-32)	-	
Test_Name	Text	Name of the test/analysis	aSyn	-	
			Hb	-	
			Hemo-globin	-	
Test_Value	Text	Value generated by sample analysis (average of value from 2 duplicates)	-	-	Out of range values reported as "above" or "below" range.
Units	Text	Units of measure	ng/ml	-	
			pg/ml	-	

Genotypes data transfer (LabData_Genotypes)

Table Description: Genotypes data transfer

View Source Methods: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor by analyzing DNA from each participant in S4 using the NeuroArray. The genetic risk scores were calculated with the default setting of "--score" option of Plink. The weights for the counted allele were given as below. Please note that the weights were derived from the case-control study which only included participants of European ancestry. The GRS might not reflect genetic burdens for people from other populations^{1,2}.

1. Nalls MA, Blauwendraat C, Vallerga CL, et al. Identification of novel risk loci, causal insights, and heritable risk for Parkinson's disease: a meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies. *Lancet Neurol* 2019; 18: 1091–102.
2. Purcell S, Neale B, Todd-Brown K, et al. PLINK: A Tool Set for Whole-Genome Association and Population-Based Linkage Analyses. *Am J Hum Genet.* 2007;81:559–575.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
RunTimeDays	Numeric	De-identified time sample analysis performed. [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Gender	Text	Gender	F	Female	
			M	Male	
Genetic_risk_score	Numeric	Genetic risk score [Derived]	-	-	
rs35095275	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs34637584	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs33939927	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
rs35801418	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs34778348	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs33949390	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs76763715	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs104893877	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs104893875	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs104893878	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs2619361	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs2583988	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs2736990	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs3857059	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs894278	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	
rs356220	Numeric	Genetic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	-	-	

HB data transfer (LabData_HB)

Table Description: IND_HB data transfer

View Source Methods: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor by measuring concentrations of hemoglobin in plasma and serum using the QuantiChrom test (BioAssay Systems, Cat. No. DIHB-250)), concentration of hemoglobin in CSF was measured using the Human Hemoglobin ELISA Quantitaton Set (Bethyl Laboratories, Cat. No. E88-134), and concentrations of hemoglobin in whole blood and saliva were measured using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay from Bethyl Laboratories (Cat. No. E88-134).

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Specimen_Type	Text	Specimen Type	Cerebro -spinal Fluid	-	
			Plasma	-	
			Serum	-	
Hemoglobin_Assay	Text	Assay Name	Bethyl	-	
			Quanti- Chrom	-	
Hemoglobin_UOM	Text	Units of Measure	ng/ml	-	
			pg/ml	-	
Hemoglobin_value	Numeric	Value generated by sample analysis	-	-	
Turbidity	Text	Turbidity	0-Clear	-	
			1- Slightly Cloudy	-	
			2- Cloudy	-	

IND data transfer (LabData_IND)

Table Description: IND data transfer

View Source Methods: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor. Dopamine transporter SPECT scan was obtained for each participant and analyzed at the radiology core for the study, Institute for Neurodegeneration. Specific binding ratios (SBR) were calculated for each region shown. Scans were also interpreted by radiologists (visual inspection, vi) to determine participant eligibility for the study (see protocol and inclusion/exclusion criteria).

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Scan_DateDays	Numeric	De-identified date of scan [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
scan_number	Numeric	Screening visit number	1		This variable is populated with a value of '1' for all records, indicating that scans were collected during participants' screening visit
gender	Text	Gender	F	Female	
			M	Male	
ligand	Text	Ligand	DAT		This variable is populated with a value of 'DAT' for all records, indicating that DATScans were collected
scan_analyzed	Text	Was the scan able to be analyzed?	No		
			Yes		
reason_scan_not_analyzed	Text	Reason the scan was not analyzed	-	-	These variables are not populated, since all participant scans were able to be analyzed
other_specify	Text	Other reason scan not analyzed	-	-	
Rcaud_SBR	Numeric	Striatal Binding Ratio Right Caudate (small)	-	-	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Rput_SBR	Numeric	Striatal Binding Ratio Right Putament (small)	-	-	
Lcaud_SBR	Numeric	Striatal Binding Ratio Left Caudate (small)	-	-	
Lput_SBR	Numeric	Striatal Binding Ratio Left Putamen (small)	-	-	
vi_score	Numeric	Visual interpretation score	Positive	Shows evidence of dopamine transporter deficit	
			Negative	Shows no evidence of dopamine transporter deficit	
			Not Assess-able	Reader was unable to assess the image	

Slide Scoring (final consensus scores) (LabData_Slide_Scoring)

Table Description: Slide Scoring (final consensus scores)

View Source Methods: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was not collected via the EDC system; it was generated by a third-party vendor. Each slide image was interpreted by 3 independent and blinded histopathology judges who rated the slides semi-quantitatively for presence of α -synuclein and density score.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CassetteNum	Text	Cassette Number	-	-	
Structure	Text	Structure; Type of Biopsy	Colon	-	
			Skin	-	
			Subma- ndibular	-	
Syn_Dens	Numeric	Density Score (pathologist consensus score used for analyses)	0	-	
			1	-	
			2	-	
			3	-	
SeqNum	Numeric	Sequence Number			
SkinRegion	Numeric	Skin Region	1	Cervical paravertebral region	This variable is populated for skin slides only; when the Structure variable equals 'Skin'
			2	Distal thigh	

Lumbar Puncture (LumbarPuncture)

Table Description: Lumbar Puncture

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 19 – Lumbar Puncture' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CSFDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
FLUORODTDays	Numeric	Date of fluoroscopy: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if a fluoroscopy is performed, where FLUORO equals '1'
LMDTDays	Numeric	Date of last intake of food: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PDMEDDTDays	Numeric	Date of most recent PD medication dosing: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant is on medication for PD, where PDMEDYN equals '1'
SPFIDTDays	Numeric	Date of lumbar spine film: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if a lumbar spine film is performed, where FLUORO equals '1'
CSFCOLL	Numeric	Lumbar puncture for collection of CSF:	1	Not Done	
			2	Collected	
			3	Partial Collection	
			4	Attempted, no collection	
LMTM	Numeric	Time of last intake of food:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
FASTSTAT	Numeric	Fasting status:	1	Fasted (minimum of 8 hours)	
			2	Low Fat Diet	
			3	Not Fasted, No Low Fat Diet	
PDMEDYN	Numeric	Is subject on medication for PD?	0	No	This value represents medication status, additional datetime information is specified as supporting variables (PDMEDDTPDays, PDMEDTM)
			1	Yes	
PDMEDTM	Numeric	Time of most recent PD medication dosing:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant is on medication for PD, where PDMEDYN equals '1'
PrePulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (pre-procedure):	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PreRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (pre-procedure):	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
PreSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
CSFTM	Numeric	Time CSF collection completed:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
CSFNEEDL	Numeric	Indicate needle used to collect CSF:	1	20g Quincke (sharp beveled) needle	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			2	22g Quincke (sharp beveled) needle	
			3	25g Quincke (sharp beveled) needle	
			4	22g Sprotte (atraumatic) needle	
			5	24g Sprotte (atraumatic) needle (preferred)	
			6	Other	
CSFMETHD	Numeric	Indicate method of collecting the CSF:	1	Gravity	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			2	Syringe suction	
LPSITE	Numeric		1	L2-L3 Interspace	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Lumbar puncture performed at the:	2	L3-L4 Interspace	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			3	L4-L5 Interspace	
			4	Other	
LPPOSITN	Numeric	Subject position when lumbar puncture performed:	1	Sitting, leaned over (preferred)	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			2	Lying, curled up on side	
			3	Other	
WBCRSLT	Numeric	White blood cell count:	-	-	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
WBCUNITB	Numeric	Units (WBC):	1	Per Cubic Millimeter	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
			2	Per Microliter	
			3	Per Liter	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
RBCRSLT	Numeric	Red blood cell count:	-	-	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
RBCUNITB	Numeric	Units (RBC):	1	Per Cubic Millimeter	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
			2	Per Microliter	
			3	Per Liter	
TOPRRSLT	Numeric	Total protein:	-	-	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
TOPRUNIT	Numeric	Units (total protein):	1	mg/dL	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture
			2	g/dL	
			3	g/L	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected. Clinical staff respond to this if part of the sample was sent to local lab for analysis, where SMPLOCAL equals '1'
FLUORO	Numeric	Was a fluoroscopy performed?	0	No	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			1	Yes	
SPFI	Numeric	Was a lumbar spine film performed?	0	No	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			1	Yes	
CSFSPNTM	Numeric	Time CSF was centrifuged:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
CSFSPNRT	Numeric	Rate of centrifugation for the CSF sample:	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of xg. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CSFCFRG	Numeric	Temperature at which CSF tube was centrifuged:	1	Room temperature	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			2	Refrigerated	
CSFALQTM	Numeric	Time CSF sample aliquotted	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
CSFVAFT	Numeric	Total volume of CSF aliquotted after centrifuging:	-	-	This variable represents volume in units of milliliters. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
CSFALQN	Numeric	Total number of aliquot tubes:	-	-	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
SMPDSCRD	Numeric	Was part of sample discarded due to a bloody tap?	0	No	This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CSFFFTM	Numeric	Time samples were frozen:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
CSFSTTMP	Numeric	Storage temperature if placed in freezer:	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
PostPulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PostRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
PostSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
CSFSPNDUR	Numeric	Duration of centrifugation: (minutes)	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of minutes. This variable is not populated for instances where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected
SMPLOCAL	Numeric	Was part of the sample sent to local lab for analyses?	0	No	This variable is not populated for instances

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Yes	where a lumbar puncture was attempted, but no sample was able to be collected

Medical History Conditions (MedHxConditions)

Table Description: Medical History Conditions

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 4B – Medical History' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
EndDTDays	Numeric	If No, End Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this only if the medical condition is no longer present at time of assessment
StartDTDays	Numeric	Start Date [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
BodySystem	Numeric	Body System	1	01 Constitutional Symptoms	
			2	02 Eyes	
			3	03 Ears, Nose, Mouth, Throat	
			4	04 Cardiovascular	
			5	05 Respiratory	
			6	06 Abdominal/GI	
			7	07 Musculoskeletal	
			8	08 Skin	
			9	09 Neurological/CNS	
			10	10 Psychiatric	
			11	11 Endocrine	
			12	12 Blood/ Hematology/ Lymphatic	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			13	13 Immunological/Allergy	
			14	14 Gynecological/Urological/ Renal	
			15	15 Other, specify	
StillPresent	Numeric	Still present?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
BodySystemOtherSpecify	Text	Specify (other body system)	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the body system is specified as '15 Other, specify'
MedHxTerm	Text	Medical History Term	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this as one item per line meaning that one participant can have multiple records

Medical History (MedicalHistory)

Table Description: Medical History

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 4B – Medical History' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CollectionDTDays	Numeric	Date medical history taken [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
HasMedHx	Numeric	Does the participant/subject have a history of any medical problems/conditions in the following body systems?	0	No	
			1	Yes	

Medical History of Parkinson’s Disease (MedicalHxPD)

Table Description: Medical History of Parkinson’s Disease

View Source Instruments: Refer to the ‘1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)’ folder within the ‘Clinical data.zip’ file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the ‘Form 4A – Medical History of Parkinson’s Disease CRF.’

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CollectionDTDays	Numeric	Date of collection: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
DopaThStartDTDays	Numeric	Date dopaminergic therapy started: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant reports having started dopaminergic therapy
DyskinesiaDTDays	Numeric	Date first appeared: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant reports experiencing dyskinesia
MotorFlucDTDays	Numeric	Date started: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant reports

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					experiencing motor fluctuation
SXMo_Dif	Numeric	Month of first symptoms as confirmed by history obtained by the physician? [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to number of months difference from consent for de-identification purposes
SXYEAR_Dif	Numeric	Year of first symptoms as confirmed by history obtained by the physician? [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to number of years difference from consent for de-identification purposes
DXMon_Dif	Numeric	Month of Initial Diagnosis? [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to number of months difference from consent for de-identification purposes
DXYEAR_Dif	Numeric	Year of Initial Diagnosis? [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to number of years difference from consent for de-identification purposes
DXTREMOR	Numeric	4-6 Hz Rest Tremor	1	Present	
			2	Absent	
			3	Unknown	
DXBRADY	Numeric	Bradykinesia	1	Present	
			2	Absent	
			3	Unknown	
DXRIGID	Numeric	Rigidity	1	Present	
			2	Absent	
			3	Unknown	
AsymOnset	Numeric	Asymmetric Onset	1	Present	
			2	Absent	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Unknown	
DopaThResp	Numeric	Substantial Response to Dopaminergic Therapy	1	Present	
			2	Absent	
			3	Unknown	
SagittalSide	Numeric	Side of body most affected:	1	Right	
			2	Left	
			3	Symmetric	
DopaThStart	Numeric	Has the subject started dopaminergic therapy?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
MotorFluc	Numeric	Motor fluctuation?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
MotorFlucOff	Numeric	Wearing off?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Dyskinesia	Numeric	Does the subject experience dyskinesia?	0	No	
			1	Yes	

MOCA (MOCA)

Table Description: MOCA

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 13 – MOCA' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
AssessmentDTDays	Numeric	Date of assessment: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Visuospatial	Numeric	Visuospatial/Executive:	Range (0-5)	-	
Naming	Numeric	Naming:	Range (0-3)	-	
Digits	Numeric	Reading list of digits:	Range (0-2)	-	
Letters	Numeric	Reading list of letters:	Range (0-1)	-	
Subtraction	Numeric	Serial 7 subtraction:	Range (0-3)	-	
LangRepeat	Numeric	Repeat:	Range (0-2)	-	
LangFluency	Numeric	Fluency:	Range (0-1)	-	
Abstraction	Numeric	Abstraction:	Range (0-2)	-	
DelayedRecall	Numeric	Delayed Recall:	Range (0-5)	-	
Orientation	Numeric	Orientation:	Range (0-6)	-	

Neurological Exam (NeuroExam)

Table Description: Neurological Exam

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 6 – Neurological Exam' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CollectionDTDays	Numeric	Date of collection: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Cranial1	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve I)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial2	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve II)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial346	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve III, IV, VI)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial5	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve V)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial7	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve VII)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial8	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve VIII)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial910	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve IX, X)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial11	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve XI)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
Cranial12	Numeric	Assessment Result (Cranial nerve XII)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
StrengthRA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle strength, right arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
StrengthLA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle strength, left arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
StrengthRL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle strength, right leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
StrengthLL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle strength, left leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
CoordinationRA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Coordination, right arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
CoordinationLA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Coordination, left arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
CoordinationRL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Coordination, right leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
CoordinationLL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Coordination, left leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
SensationRA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Sensation, right arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
SensationLA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Sensation, left arm)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
SensationRL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Sensation, right leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
SensationLL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Sensation, left leg)	1	Normal	
			2	Abnormal	
			3	Not tested	
			4	Unable to test	
ReflexRA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle stretch reflex, right arm)	1	Absent	
			2	Hypoactive	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Normal	
			4	Hyperactive, no clonus	
			5	Hyperactive, clonus	
			6	Not tested	
			7	Unable to test	
ReflexLA	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle stretch reflex, left arm)	1	Absent	
			2	Hypoactive	
			3	Normal	
			4	Hyperactive, no clonus	
			5	Hyperactive, clonus	
			6	Not tested	
			7	Unable to test	
ReflexRL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle stretch reflex, right leg)	1	Absent	
			2	Hypoactive	
			3	Normal	
			4	Hyperactive, no clonus	
			5	Hyperactive, clonus	
			6	Not tested	
			7	Unable to test	
ReflexLL	Numeric	Assessment Result (Muscle stretch reflex, left leg)	1	Absent	
			2	Hypoactive	
			3	Normal	
			4	Hyperactive, no clonus	
			5	Hyperactive, clonus	
			6	Not tested	
			7	Unable to test	
PlantarR	Numeric	Assessment Result (Plantar response, right)	1	Flexor	
			2	Extensor	
			3	Indeterminate	
			4	Not tested	
			5	Unable to test	
PlantarL	Numeric		1	Flexor	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Assessment Result (Plantar response, left)	2	Extensor	
			3	Indeterminate	
			4	Not tested	
			5	Unable to test	
Cranial1Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve I)	-	-	
Cranial2Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve II)	-	-	
Cranial346Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve III, IV, VI)	-	-	
Cranial5Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve V)	-	-	
Cranial7Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve VII)	-	-	
Cranial8Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve VIII)	-	-	
Cranial910Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve IX, X)	-	-	
Cranial11Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve XI)	-	-	
Cranial12Descrip	Text	Description (Cranial nerve XII)	-	-	
CoordinationRADescrip	Text	Description (Coordination, right arm)	-	-	
CoordinationLADescrip	Text	Description (Coordination, left arm)	-	-	
CoordinationRLDescrip	Text	Description (Coordination, right leg)	-	-	
CoordinationLLDescrip	Text	Description (Coordination, left leg)	-	-	
SensationRADescrip	Text	Description (Sensation, right arm)	-	-	
SensationLADescrip	Text	Description (Sensation, left arm)	-	-	
SensationRLDescrip	Text	Description (Sensation, right leg)	-	-	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
SensationLLDescrip	Text	Description (Sensation, left leg)	-	-	
ReflexRADDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle stretch reflex, right arm)	-	-	
ReflexLADDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle stretch reflex, left arm)	-	-	
ReflexRLDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle stretch reflex, right leg)	-	-	
ReflexLLDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle stretch reflex, left leg)	-	-	
PlantarRDescrip	Text	Description (Plantar response, left)	-	-	
PlantarLDescrip	Text	Description (Plantar response, right)	-	-	
StrengthRADDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle strength, right arm)	-	-	
StrengthLADDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle strength, left arm)	-	-	
StrengthRLDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle strength, right leg)	-	-	
StrengthLLDescrip	Text	Description (Muscle strength, left leg)	-	-	

Physical Exam (PhysicalExam)

Table Description: Physical Exam

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 7 – Physical Exam' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Skin	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Skin)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
SkinSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Skin)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Head	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Head/Neck/Lymphatic)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
HeadSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Head/Neck/Lymphatic)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Eyes	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Eyes)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
EyesSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Eyes)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Ears	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Ears, Nose, Throat)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
EarsSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Ears, Nose, Throat)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Lungs	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Lungs)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
LungsSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Lungs)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Cardio	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Cardiovascular)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
CardioSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Cardiovascular)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Abdomen	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Abdomen)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
AbdomenSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Abdomen)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Musc	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Musculoskeletal)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
MuscSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Musculoskeletal)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Neuro	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Neurological)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
NeuroSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Neurological)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Psych	Numeric	Abnormality Present? (Psychiatric)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
PsychSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Psychiatric)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
Other	Numeric		0	No	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Abnormality Present? (Other)	1	Yes	
			2	Not Done	
OtherDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Other)	-	-	
OtherSign	Numeric	Is Abnormality Clinically Significant? (Other)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if an abnormality is present
			1	Yes	
OtherSpecify	Text	Specify (Other):	-	-	
PsychDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Psychiatric)	-	-	
NeuroDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Neurological)	-	-	
MuscDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Musculoskeletal)	-	-	
EyesDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Eyes)	-	-	
SkinDescribe	Text	Describe Abnormality (Skin)	-	-	

Protocol Deviation (ProtocolDev)

Table Description: Protocol Deviation

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was reported by clinical staff via the 'Form 26 – Protocol Deviation' CRF when a protocol deviation (any departure from the study procedures or treatment plans as specified in the IRB-approved protocol) occurred. Several protocol deviations may exist for the same participant, if they occurred at distinct points in time throughout the study.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
DeviationDTDays	Numeric	Date of protocol deviation: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
SiteAwareDTDays	Numeric	Date site became aware of deviation: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
DeviationType	Numeric	Type of deviation:	1	Informed consent	
			2	Protocol compliance	
			3	Other	
Consent		Choose the option that best describes the informed consent deviation:	1	Failure to obtain informed consent	Clinical staff respond to this if 'Informed Consent' is reported as the protocol deviation type
			2	No documentation of informed consent	
			3	Incomplete documentation of informed consent	
			4	Informed consent obtained after initiation of study procedures	
			5	Informed consent obtained by someone other than individuals authorized by IRB to obtain consent	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			6	Missing signed and dated consent form	
			7	Subject signed expired or incorrect version of the consent form	
			8	Other	
Compliance	Numeric	Choose the option that best describes the protocol compliance deviation:	1	Enrollment of a subject who did not meet all inclusion/exclusion criteria	Clinical staff respond to this if 'Protocol Compliance' is reported as the protocol deviation type
			2	Failure to conduct a study visit	
			3	Failure to complete all study procedures at a study visit as specified	
			4	Study procedures/visits conducted out of window	
			5	Protocol-specified study therapy not administered as directed	
			6	Other	
Termination	Numeric	Did this deviation result in termination from the study?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
DeviationDescrip	Text	Provide a detailed description of the protocol deviation:	-	-	

Collection form for Saliva Sample (SalivaSample)

Table Description: Collection form for Saliva Sample

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 18 – Saliva Sampling' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
TobaccoUse	Numeric	Tobacco use?	1	Current	
			2	Former	
			3	Never	
TobaccoTimeSinceLast	Numeric	Time since last use?	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if participant has reported currently or formerly using tobacco
TobaccoTimeUnit	Numeric	-	1	Days	
			2	Weeks	
			3	Months	
AlcoholUse	Numeric	Alcohol use?	1	Current	
			2	Former	
			3	Never	
AlcoholTimeSinceLast	Numeric	Time since last use?	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if participant has reported currently or formerly using alcohol
AlcoholTimeUnit	Numeric	-	1	Days	
			2	Weeks	
			3	Months	
SalivaSampleCollected	Numeric	Saliva sample collected:	1	Not Done	
			2	Collected	
			3	Partial Collection	
			4	Attempted, no collection	
CollectionStartTime	Numeric	Collection start time:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
CollectionEndTime	Numeric	Collection end time:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
SalivaAmountCollected	Numeric	Amount of saliva collected:	-	-	This variable represents amount in units of mL
ProteaseInhibAmount	Numeric	Amount of protease inhibitor added to saliva sample:	-	-	This variable represents amount in units of microliters
TimeCentrifugeBegun	Numeric	Time centrifuge was begun:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
CentrifugationRate	Numeric	Rate of centrifugation:	-	-	This variable represents rate in units of xg
CentrifugationDuration	Numeric	Duration of centrifugation:	-	-	This variable represents duration in units of minutes
CentrifugedTemp	Numeric	Indicate temperature at which tubes were centrifuged:	1	Room temperature	
			2	Refrigerated	
TimeTubesInFreezer	Numeric	Time tubes placed in freezer:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
StorageTemp	Numeric	Storage temperature:	-	-	This variable represents temperature in units of Celsius
NumberOfTubes	Numeric	Total number of supernatant aliquot tubes:	-	-	
LastFoodOrLiquid	Numeric	Hours since last intake of food or liquid?	-	-	This variable represents time in units of hours
LastOralHygiene	Numeric	Hours since last use of oral hygiene products?	-	-	This variable represents time in units of hours
ProteaseManufacturer	Text	Protease inhibitor manufacturer:	-	-	
ProteaseLotNum	Text	Protease inhibitor lot #:	-	-	

SCOPA-AUT-EN (SCOPA)

Table Description: SCOPA-AUT-EN

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 11 – SCOPA-AUT-EN' CRF. This instrument is designed to understand to what extent in the past month a participant has had problems with various bodily functions, such as difficulty passing urine, or excessive sweating.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
SCAU1	Numeric	In the past month, have you had difficulty swallowing or have you choked?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU2	Numeric	In the past month, has saliva dribbled out of your mouth?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU3	Numeric	In the past month, has food ever become stuck in your throat?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU4	Numeric	In the past month, did you ever have the feeling during a meal that you were full <u>very quickly</u> ?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU5	Numeric	Constipation is a blockage of the bowel, a condition in which someone has a bowel movement twice a week or less. In the past month, have you had problems with constipation?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU6	Numeric		0	Never	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		In the past month, did you have to strain hard to pass stools?	1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU7	Numeric	In the past month, have you had involuntary loss of stools?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU8	Numeric	In the past month, have you had difficulty retaining urine?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU9	Numeric	In the past month, have you had involuntary loss of urine?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU10	Numeric	In the past month, have you had the feeling that after passing urine your bladder was not completely empty?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU11	Numeric	In the past month, has the stream of urine been weak?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU12	Numeric	In the past month, have you had to pass urine again within 2 hours of the previous time?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU13	Numeric	In the past month, have you had to pass urine at night?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU14	Numeric		0	Never	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		In the past month, <u>when standing up</u> have you had the feeling of either becoming lightheaded, or no longer being able to see properly, or no longer being able to think clearly?	1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU15	Numeric	In the past month, did you become light-headed after standing for <u>some time</u> ?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU16	Numeric	Have you fainted in the past <u>6 months</u> ?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU17	Numeric	In the past month, have you ever perspired excessively <u>during the day</u> ?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU18	Numeric	In the past month, have you ever perspired excessively <u>during the night</u> ?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU19	Numeric	In the past month, have your eyes ever been over-sensitive to bright light?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU20	Numeric	In the past month, how often have you had trouble tolerating cold?	0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU21	Numeric		0	Never	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		In the past month, how often have you had trouble tolerating heat?	1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU22	Numeric	In the past month, have you been impotent (unable to have or maintain an erection)?	-1	Not applicable	Clinical staff respond to this for male participants only
			0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU23	Numeric	In the past month, how often have you been unable to ejaculate?	-1	Not applicable	Clinical staff respond to this for female participants only
			0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU23A	Numeric	In the past month, have you taken medication for an erection disorder? (If so, which medication?)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SCAU24	Numeric	In the past month, was your vagina too dry during sexual activity?	-1	Not applicable	Clinical staff respond to this for female participants only
			0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU25	Numeric	In the past month, have you had difficulty reaching an orgasm?	-1	Not applicable	Clinical staff respond to this for female participants only
			0	Never	
			1	Sometimes	
			2	Regularly	
			3	Often	
SCAU26A	Numeric	In the past month, have you used medication for constipation?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SCAU26B	Numeric		0	No	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		In the past month, have you used medication for urinary problems?	1	Yes	
SCAU26C	Numeric	In the past month, have you used medication for blood pressure?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SCAU26D	Numeric	In the past month, have you used medication for other symptoms? (<i>not symptoms related to Parkinson's Disease</i>)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SCAU23AT	Text	Specify (erection medication):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if a participant reports having used medication for an erection disorder
SCAU26AT	Text	Specify (constipation medication):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if a participant reports having used medication for constipation
SCAU26BT	Text	Specify (urinary medication):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if a participant reports having used medication for urinary problems
SCAU26CT	Text	Specify (blood pressure medication):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if a participant reports having used medication for blood pressure
SCAU26DT	Text	Specify (other medication):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if a participant reports having used medication for other symptoms not related to Parkinson's disease

Score Calculations (Scores)

Table Description: Score Calculations

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form # – TBD' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
updrs1_score	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Part I Score [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPDRS table: Cognitive, Hallucinations, Depressed, Anxious, Apathy, DDS, Sleep, DaytimeSleep, Sensations, Urinary, Constipation, LightHeaded, Fatigue
updrs2_score	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Part II Score [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPDRS table: Speech, Drool, ChewSwallow, Eat, Dress, Hygiene, Handwriting, Activities, BedTurning, Tremor, BedOut, WalkingBalance, Freezing
updrs3_score	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Part III Score (OFF) [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPDRS table: SpeechOff, FacialOff, RigidityNeckOff, RigidityRUEOff, RigidityLUEOff, RigidityRLEOff, RigidityLLEOff,

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					FingerRightOff, FingerLeftOff, HandRightOff, HandLeftOff, ProRightOff, ProLeftOff, ToeRightOff, ToeLeftOff, LegRightOff, LegLeftOff, ChairOff, GaitOff, GaitFreezingOff, StabilityOff, PostureOff, GlobalOff, PostTremRightOff, PostTremLeftOff, KinTremRightOff, KinTremLeftOff, RestTremRUEOff, RestTremLUEOff, RestTremRLEOff, RestTremLLEOff, RestTremLipOff, RestConstOff
updrs3_score_on	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Part III Score (ON) [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPDRS table: SpeechOn, FacialOn, RigidityNeckOn, RigidityRUEOn, RigidityLUEOn, RigidityRLEOn, RigidityLLEOn, FingerRightOn, FingerLeftOn, HandRightOn, HandLeftOn, ProRightOn, ProLeftOn,

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					ToeRightOn, ToeLeftOn, LegRightOn, LegLeftOn, ChairOn, GaitOn, GaitFreezingOn, StabilityOn, PostureOn, GlobalOn, PostTremRightOn, PostTremLeftOn, KinTremRightOn, KinTremLeftOn, RestTremRUEOn, RestTremLUEOn, RestTremRLEOn, RestTremLLEOn, RestTremLipOn, RestConstOn
updrs4_score	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Part IV Score [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPDRS table: DyskinTime, DyskinFunc, OffStateTime, FluctFunc, FluctComp, OffStateDystonia
updrs_totscore	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Total Score (OFF) [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the all variables in the UPDRS table from MDS-UPDRS Parts I, II, III (OFF)
updrs_totscore_on	Numeric	MDS-UPDRS Total Score (ON) [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the all variables in the UPDRS table from MDS-UPDRS Parts I, II, III (ON)

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
scopa	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Total Score [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing all sub-scores, as detailed below
scopa_gi	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Gastrointestinal Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For questions SCAU1 - SCAU7, in the SCOPA table, add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response. Derived by summing SCAU1 – SCAU7
scopa_ur	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Urinary Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For questions SCAU8 – SCAU13, in the SCOPA table, add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response. Derived by summing SCAU8 – SCAU13
scopa_cv	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Cardiovascular Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For questions SCAU14 – SCAU16, in the SCOPA table, add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response. Derived by summing SCAU14 – SCAU16
scopa_therm	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Thermoregulatory Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For questions SCAU17, SCAU18, SCAU20, SCAU21 add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					Derived by summing SCAU17, SCAU18, SCAU20, SCAU21
scopa_pm	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Pupillomotor Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For question SCAU19, in the SCOPA table, add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response
scopa_sex	Numeric	SCOPA-AUT Sexual Dysfunction Subscore [Derived]	-	-	For questions SCAU22 – SCAU25, in the SCOPA table, add 0 points for each response of “-1”. Otherwise, add the number of points in response. Derived for male participants by summing SCAU22 – SCAU23. Derived for female participants by summing SCAU24 – SCAU25
LEDD	Numeric	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose [Derived]	-	-	Due to the complexity of calculating the Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD), a separate document, ‘Methods_LEDD_Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose.docx’, is shared. Of note, this methods document was originally

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					prepared as part of the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study, however the same methods were used for the original S4 analysis.
upsit	Numeric	UPSIT Raw Score [Derived]	-	-	Derived by summing the following variables from the UPSIT table: Booklet1 – Booklet4
upsit_cat	Numeric	UPSIT Category (Age- and Sex-Adjusted) [Derived]	1	Normosmia (Normal)	A value of '1' is assigned if male participants have an UPSIT Raw Score greater than or equal to 34 -OR- greater than or equal to 35 for female participants
			2	Hyposmia (Mild, Moderate, or Severe Microsmia)	A value of '2' is assigned if male participants have an UPSIT Raw Score between 19 – 33 -OR- between 19 – 34 for female participants
			3	Anosmia (Total loss of smell)	A value of '3' is assigned if participants (regardless of sex) have an UPSIT Raw Score less than 19
moca	Numeric	MOCA Total Score (Education-Adjusted) [Derived]	-	-	Unadjusted score derived by summing the following variables from the MOCA table: Visuospatial, Naming, Digits, Letters, Subtraction, LangRepeat, LangFluency,

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					Abstraction, DelayedRecall, Orientation To calculate education adjusted score: If YearsOfEducation \leq 12 and Unadjusted Score < 30, add 1 more point to score. If YearsOfEducation > 12, do not add any more points to score
disease_duration	Numeric	Disease duration (months) [Derived]	-	-	This variable was derived as the number of months between the date of diagnosis and date of consent for de-identification purposes

Skin Biopsy (SkinBiopsy)

Table Description: Skin Biopsy

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 20 – Skin Biopsy' CRF and is a parent table to the '*Distal Thigh Biopsy (ThighBiopsy)*' and '*Cervical Paravertebral Biopsy (CervicalBiopsy)*' tables.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Collected	Numeric	Skin biopsy collected:	1	Not Done	
			2	Collected	
			3	Partial Collection	
			4	Attempted, no collection	
Anesthesia	Numeric	Type of anesthesia used?	1	Lidocaine	
			2	None	
			3	Other	
Tool	Numeric	Use of 3 mm punch biopsy tool?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
NotCollectedSpecify	Text	If collection was not completed, why?	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if skin collection was not completed
AnesthesiaSpecify	Text	Specify (anesthesia):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the type of anesthesia used is specified as 'Other'
DeviceSpecify	Text	If another device was used please list:	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the biopsy tool used is not a 3mm punch biopsy tool; specified as 'No' in the Tool variable
FormulinManu	Text	Formalin Manufacturer:	-	-	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
FormulinLotNum	Text	Formalin Lot#:	-	-	
ZamboniManu	Text	Zamboni Manufacturer:	-	-	
ZamboniLotNum	Text	Zamboni Lot#:	-	-	
Comments	Text	Comments:	-	-	

Skin Pathology (SkinPath)

Table Description: Skin Pathology

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Skin Pathology' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CassetteNum	Text	Cassette #:	-	-	
SeqNum1	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 1)	-	-	
Compartment11	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density11	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment11_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 1, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density11_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 1, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment12	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density12	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment12_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 2, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density12_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 2, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment13	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density13	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment13_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 1, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density13_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
SeqNum2	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 2)	-	-	
Compartment21	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density21	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment21_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 1, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density21_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment22	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density22	Numeric		0	0	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 2, dermis)	1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment22_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 2, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density22_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment23	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density23	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment23_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density23_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 2, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
SeqNum3	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 3)	-	-	
Compartment31	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density31	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 1, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment31_hypo	Numeric		0	No	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
		Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 1, hypodermis)	1	Yes	
Density31_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 1, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment32	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density32	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 2, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment32_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 2, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density32_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 2, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment33	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density33	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 3, dermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Compartment33_hypo	Numeric	Compartment present? (slide 3, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	No	
			1	Yes	
Density33_hypo	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 3, hypodermis)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	3	

Study Termination (StudyTerm)

Table Description: Study Termination

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 27 – Study Termination' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CompletionDTDays	Numeric	Date subject completed participation in study: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
LastContactDTDays	Numeric	Date of last communication from subject, or clinical update: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
CompleteAllProcedures	Numeric	Did subject complete all procedures? [Derived]	0	No	This variable was derived from the primary reason for termination
			1	Yes	
ExplainWhy	Numeric	Primary reason for termination: (select one)	1	Subject completed study procedures per protocol	This variable is blank for participants who completed study procedures per the protocol
			2	Subject chose to discontinue the study	
			3	Site PI chose to discontinue subject participation	
			4	Subject is lost to follow up	
			5	Death	
			6	Other	

Subject Status (SubjectStatus)

Table Description: Subject Status

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 1 – Informed Consent' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
PDStage	Numeric	Current Parkinson's disease stage	1	Early untreated	
			2	Moderate	
			3	Advanced	
			4	N/A – Healthy Control	

Submandibular Gland Biopsy (SubmanBiopsy)

Table Description: Submandibular Gland Biopsy

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 22 – Submandibular Gland Biopsy' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Collected	Numeric	Submandibular gland biopsy collected:	1	Not Done	
			2	Collected	
			3	Partial Collection	
			4	Attempted, no collection	
PrePulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PreRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
PreSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PreTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (pre-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
Anesthesia	Numeric	Type of anesthesia used?	1	Lidocaine	
			2	None	
			3	Other	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Needle	Numeric	Use of 16-gauge core biopsy needle?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
SagittalSide	Numeric	Side of biopsy procedure:	1	Right	
			2	Left	
CompletedTM	Numeric	Time for completion of biopsy procedure	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
FormulinTM	Numeric	Time sample placed in formalin:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
ChilledTM	Numeric	Time sample chilled:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
SampleNum	Numeric	Number of tissue samples collected:	-	-	
Cassette1	Text	Pink Cassette# (1):	-	-	
Cassette2	Text	Pink Cassette# (2):	-	-	
Cassette3	Text	Pink Cassette# (3):	-	-	
Cassette4	Text	Pink Cassette# (4):	-	-	
Cassette5	Text	Pink Cassette# (5):	-	-	
PostPulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
PostRespiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
PostSystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostDiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic; post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
PostTemp	Numeric	Temperature measurement (post-procedure)	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
NotCollectedSpecify	Text	If collection was not completed, why?	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if submandibular gland

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					sample collection was not completed
AnesthesiaSpecify	Text	Specify (anesthesia):	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the type of anesthesia used is specified as 'Other'
DeviceSpecify	Text	If another device was used please list:	-	-	Clinical staff respond to this if the biopsy tool used is not a 16-gauge core biopsy needle; specified as 'No' in the Needle variable
FormulinManu	Text	Formalin Manufacturer:	-	-	
FormulinLotNum	Text	Formalin Lot#:	-	-	
Comments	Text	Comments:	-	-	

Submandibular Pathology (SubmanPath)

Table Description: Submandibular Pathology

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Submandibular Pathology' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CassetteNum	Text	Cassette #:	-	-	
SeqNum1	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 1)	-	-	
Density11	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 1)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density12	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 2)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density13	Numeric	Density Score (slide 1, biopsy 3)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
SeqNum2	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 2)	-	-	
Density21	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 1)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density22	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 2)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density23	Numeric	Density Score (slide 2, biopsy 3)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	3	
SeqNum3	Numeric	Sequential Number (slide 3)	-	-	
Density31	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 1)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density32	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 2)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	
Density33	Numeric	Density Score (slide 3, biopsy 3)	0	0	
			1	1	
			2	2	
			3	3	

Distal Thigh Biopsy (ThighBiopsy)

Table Description: Distal Thigh Biopsy

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 20 – Skin Biopsy' CRF and is a child table to the 'SkinBiopsy' table.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
CassetteNum	Text	White Cassette#	-	-	
SampleNum	Numeric	# of samples in cassette	-	-	
SagittalSide	Numeric	Side of biopsy	1	Right	
			2	Left	
Closure	Numeric	Closure	1	Steri-strip/bandaid	
			2	Suture	
BiopsyTM	Numeric	Time of biopsy	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
Fixative	Numeric	Type of fixative used	1	Formalin	
			2	Zamboni's	
FixativeTM	Numeric	Time sample placed in fixative	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock
ChilledTM	Numeric	Time sample was chilled	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock

MDS-UPDRS (UPDRS)

Table Description: MDS-UPDRS

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants via the 'Form 9 – MDS-UPDRS Complete' CRF. This clinical measurement was administered by clinical staff per the following [instructions](#) and was reported in non-uniform visits for any given participant; meaning one participant could have reported at their screening visit while a different participant did at another timepoint. In these instances, data collected at *either* timepoint represents cross-sectional data for that participant regardless of which timepoint it was collected in. The MDS-UPDRS has four parts: Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), Part II (motor experiences of daily living), Part III (motor examination) and Part IV (motor complications).

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
AssessmentDTDays	Numeric	Date of assessment: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PDMedDTDays	Numeric	What is the date and time the subject last took their Parkinson's medication? [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
PDMedYN	Numeric	Is the subject taking medication for their Parkinson's?	0	No	
			1	Yes	
PDMedAbstain	Numeric	If so, was the subject able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for the visit?	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if the participant reports taking medication for their Parkinson's disease
			1	Yes	
PDMedTM	Numeric	What is the date and time the subject last took their Parkinson's medication?	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. Clinical staff respond to this if the participant reports taking medication for their Parkinson's disease
SourceRater	Numeric	Source of information	1	Patient	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Caregiver	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			3	Patient + Caregiver	
Cognitive	Numeric	Cognitive impairment	0	Normal: No cognitive impairment.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			1	Slight: Impairment appreciated by patient or caregiver with no concrete interference with the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			2	Mild: Clinically evident cognitive dysfunction, but only minimal interference with the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			3	Moderate: Cognitive deficits interfere with but do not preclude the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			4	Severe: Cognitive dysfunction precludes the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
Hallucinations	Numeric	Hallucinations and psychosis	0	Normal: No hallucinations or psychotic behavior.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Slight: Illusions or non-formed hallucinations, but patient recognizes them without loss of insight.	experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			2	Mild: Formed hallucinations independent of environmental stimuli. No loss of insight.	
			3	Moderate: Formed hallucinations with loss of insight.	
			4	Severe: Patient has delusions or paranoia.	
Depressed	Numeric	Depressed mood	0	Normal: No depressed mood.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			1	Slight: Episodes of depressed mood that are not sustained for more than one day at a time. No interference with patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			2	Mild: Depressed mood that is sustained over days, but without interference with normal activities and social interactions.	
			3	Moderate: Depressed mood that interferes with, but does not preclude, the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			4	Severe: Depressed mood precludes patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
Anxious	Numeric	Anxious mood	0	Normal: No anxious feelings.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			1	Slight: Anxious feelings present but not sustained for more than one day at a time. No interference with patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			2	Mild: Anxious feelings are sustained over more than one day at a time, but without interference with patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			3	Moderate: Anxious feelings interfere with, but do not preclude, the patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
			4	Severe: Anxious feelings preclude patient's ability to carry out normal activities and social interactions.	
Apathy	Numeric	Apathy	0	Normal: No apathy.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical
			1	Slight: Apathy appreciated by patient and/or caregiver, but no interference with daily	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				activities and social interactions.	staff on behalf of a participant
			2	Mild: Apathy interferes with isolated activities and social interactions.	
			3	Moderate: Apathy interferes with most activities and social interactions.	
			4	Severe: Passive and withdrawn, complete loss of initiative.	
DDS	Numeric	Features of DDS	0	Normal: No problems present.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant
			1	Slight: Problems are present but usually do not cause any difficulties for the patient or family/caregiver.	
			2	Mild: Problems are present and usually cause a few difficulties in the patient's personal and family life.	
			3	Moderate: Problems are present and usually cause a lot of difficulties in the patient's personal and family life.	
			4	Severe: Problems are present and preclude the patient's ability to carry out normal activities or social interactions or to maintain previous standards in personal and family life.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
SourcePatient	Numeric	Who is filling out questionnaire	1	Patient	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			2	Caregiver	
			3	Patient + Caregiver	
Sleep	Numeric	Sleep problems	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: Sleep problems are present but usually do not cause trouble getting a full night of sleep.	
			2	Mild: Sleep problems usually cause some difficulties getting a full night of sleep.	
			3	Moderate: Sleep problems cause a lot of difficulties getting a full night of sleep, but I still usually sleep for more than half the night.	
			4	Severe: I usually do not sleep for most of the night.	
DaytimeSleep	Numeric	Daytime sleepiness	0	Normal: No daytime sleepiness.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: Daytime sleepiness occurs but I can resist and I stay awake.	
			2	Mild: Sometimes I fall asleep when alone and relaxing. For example, while reading or watching TV.	
			3	Moderate: I sometimes fall asleep when I should not. For	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				example, while eating or talking with other people.	
			4	Severe: I often fall asleep when I should not. For example, while eating or talking with other people.	
Sensations	Numeric	Pain and other sensations	0	Normal: No uncomfortable feelings.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I have these feelings. However, I can do things and be with other people without difficulty.	
			2	Mild: These feelings cause some problems when I do things or am with other people.	
			3	Moderate: These feelings cause a lot of problems, but they do not stop me from doing things or being with other people.	
			4	Severe: These feelings stop me from doing things or being with other people.	
Urinary	Numeric	Urinary problems	0	Normal: No urine control problems.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I need to urinate often or urgently. However, these problems do not cause difficulties with my daily activities.	
			2	Mild: Urine problems cause some difficulties with my	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				daily activities. However, I do not have urine accidents.	
			3	Moderate: Urine problems cause a lot of difficulties with my daily activities, including urine accidents.	
			4	Severe: I cannot control my urine and use a protective garment or have a bladder tube.	
Constipation	Numeric	Constipation problems	0	Normal: No constipation.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I have been constipated. I use extra effort to move my bowels. However, this problem does not disturb my activities or my being comfortable.	
			2	Mild: Constipation causes me to have some troubles doing things or being comfortable.	
			3	Moderate: Constipation causes me to have a lot of trouble doing things or being comfortable. However, it does not stop me from doing anything.	
			4	Severe: I usually need physical help from someone else to empty my bowels.	
LightHeaded	Numeric	Light headedness on standing	0	Normal: No dizzy or foggy feelings.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by
			1	Slight: Dizzy or foggy feelings occur. However, they do not	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				cause me troubles doing things.	participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			2	Mild: Dizzy or foggy feelings cause me to hold on to something, but I do not need to sit or lie back down.	
			3	Moderate: Dizzy or foggy feelings cause me to sit or lie down to avoid fainting or falling.	
			4	Severe: Dizzy or foggy feelings cause me to fall or faint.	
Fatigue	Numeric	Fatigue	0	Normal: No fatigue.	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: Fatigue occurs. However it does not cause me troubles doing things or being with people.	
			2	Mild: Fatigue causes me some troubles doing things or being with people.	
			3	Moderate: Fatigue causes me a lot of troubles doing things or being with people. However, it does not stop me from doing anything.	
			4	Severe: Fatigue stops me from doing things or being with people.	
Speech	Numeric	Speech	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part I (non-motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by
			1	Slight: My speech is soft, slurred or uneven, but it does	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				not cause others to ask me to repeat myself.	participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			2	Mild: My speech causes people to ask me to occasionally repeat myself, but not everyday.	
			3	Moderate: My speech is unclear enough that others ask me to repeat myself every day even though most of my speech is understood.	
			4	Severe: Most or all of my speech cannot be understood.	
Drool	Numeric	Saliva and drooling	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I have too much saliva, but do not drool.	
			2	Mild: I have some drooling during sleep, but none when I am awake.	
			3	Moderate: I have some drooling when I am awake, but I usually do not need tissues or a handkerchief.	
			4	Severe: I have so much drooling that I regularly need to use tissues or a handkerchief to protect my clothes.	
ChewSwallow	Numeric	Chewing and swallowing	0	Normal: No problems.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Slight: I am aware of slowness in my chewing or increased effort at swallowing, but I do not choke or need to have my food specially prepared.	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			2	Mild: I need to have my pills cut or my food specially prepared because of chewing or swallowing problems, but I have not choked over the past week.	
			3	Moderate. I choked at least once in the past week.	
			4	Severe: Because of chewing and swallowing problems, I need a feeding tube.	
Eat	Numeric	Eating tasks	0	Normal: Not at all (No problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am slow, but I do not need any help handling my food and have not had food spills while eating.	
			2	Mild: I am slow with my eating and have occasional food spills. I may need help with a few tasks such as cutting meat.	
			3	Moderate: I need help with many eating tasks but can manage some alone.	
			4	Severe: I need help for most or all eating tasks.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Dress	Numeric	Dressing	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am slow but I do not need help.	
			2	Mild: I am slow and need help for a few dressing tasks (buttons, bracelets).	
			3	Moderate: I need help for many dressing tasks.	
			4	Severe: I need help for most or all dressing tasks.	
Hygiene	Numeric	Hygiene	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am slow but I do not need any help.	
			2	Mild: I need someone else to help me with some hygiene tasks.	
			3	Moderate: I need help for many hygiene tasks.	
			4	Severe: I need help for most or all of my hygiene tasks.	
Handwriting	Numeric	Handwriting	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: My writing is slow, clumsy or uneven, but all words are clear.	
			2	Mild: Some words are unclear and difficult to read.	
			3	Moderate: Many words are unclear and difficult to read.	
			4	Severe: Most or all words cannot be read.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Activities	Numeric	Doing hobbies and other activities	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am a bit slow but do these activities easily.	
			2	Mild: I have some difficulty doing these activities.	
			3	Moderate: I have major problems doing these activities, but still do most.	
			4	Severe: I am unable to do most or all of these activities.	
BedTurning	Numeric	Turning in bed	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I have a bit of trouble turning, but I do not need any help.	
			2	Mild I have a lot of trouble turning and need occasional help from someone else.	
			3	Moderate: To turn over I often need help from someone else.	
			4	Severe: I am unable to turn over without help from someone else.	
Tremor	Numeric	Tremor	0	Normal: Not at all. I have no shaking or tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: Shaking or tremor occurs but does not cause problems with any activities.	
			2	Mild: Shaking or tremor causes problems with only a few activities.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: Shaking or tremor causes problems with many of my daily activities.	
			4	Severe: Shaking or tremor causes problems with most or all activities.	
BedOut	Numeric	Getting out of bed	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am slow or awkward, but I usually can do it on my first try.	
			2	Mild: I need more than one try to get up or need occasional help.	
			3	Moderate: I sometimes need help to get up, but most times I can still do it on my own.	
			4	Severe: I need help most or all of the time.	
WalkingBalance	Numeric	Walking and balance	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I am slightly slow or may drag a leg. I never use a walking aid.	
			2	Mild: I occasionally use a walking aid, but I do not need any help from another person.	
			3	Moderate: I usually use a walking aid (cane, walker) to walk safely without falling.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				However, I do not usually need the support of another person.	
			4	Severe: I usually use the support of another persons to walk safely without falling.	
Freezing	Numeric	Freezing	0	Normal: Not at all (no problems).	This variable corresponds to Part II (motor experiences of daily living), and is reported by participants, caregivers, or a combination of both
			1	Slight: I briefly freeze but I can easily start walking again. I do not need help from someone else or a walking aid (cane or walker) because of freezing.	
			2	Mild: I freeze and have trouble starting to walk again, but I do not need someone's help or a walking aid (cane or walker) because of freezing.	
			3	Moderate: When I freeze I have a lot of trouble starting to walk again and, because of freezing, I sometimes need to use a walking aid or need someone else's help.	
			4	Severe: Because of freezing, most or all of the time, I need to use a walking aid or someone's help.	
AssesTMOff	Numeric	Time of assessment:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock. This variable corresponds

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
SpeechOff	Numeric	Speech (off medication)	0	Normal: No speech problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Loss of modulation, diction or volume, but still all words easy to understand.	
			2	Mild: Loss of modulation, diction, or volume, with a few words unclear, but the overall sentences easy to follow.	
			3	Moderate: Speech is difficult to understand to the point that some, but not most, sentences are poorly understood.	
			4	Severe: Most speech is difficult to understand or unintelligible.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
FacialOff	Numeric	Facial expression (off medication)	0	Normal: Normal facial expression.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Minimal masked facies manifested only by decreased frequency of blinking.	
			2	Mild: In addition to decreased eye-blink frequency, Masked facies present in the lower face as well, namely fewer movements around the mouth, such as less spontaneous smiling, but lips not parted.	
			3	Moderate: Masked facies with lips parted some of the time when the mouth is at rest.	
			4	Severe: Masked facies with lips parted most of the time when the mouth is at rest.	
RigidityNeckOff	Numeric	Rigidity – Neck (off medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				motion is achieved with effort.	participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityRUEOff	Numeric	Rigidity – RUE (off medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of motion is achieved with effort.	
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityLUEOff	Numeric	Rigidity – LUE(off medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				motion is achieved with effort.	participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityRLEOff	Numeric	Rigidity – RLE (off medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of motion is achieved with effort.	
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityLLEOff	Numeric	Rigidity – LLE (off medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				motion is achieved with effort.	participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
FingerRightOff	Numeric	Finger Tapping Right Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the 10 taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during tapping; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the 10-tap sequence.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during tapping or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
FingerLeftOff	Numeric	Finger Tapping Left Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the 10 taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during tapping; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the 10-tap sequence.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during tapping or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
HandRightOff	Numeric	Hand movements - Right Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st open-and-close sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
HandLeftOff	Numeric	Hand movements - Left Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				decrements near the end of the task.	poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st open-and-close sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ProRightOff	Numeric	Pronation - Supination Movements Right Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the sequence.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the sequence.	abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st supination-pronation sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ProLeftOff	Numeric	Pronation - Supination Movements Left Hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the sequence.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				decrements midway in the sequence.	in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st supination-pronation sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ToeRightOff	Numeric	Toe tapping - Right foot (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the ten taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the tapping movements; b) mild slowing; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
ToeLeftOff	Numeric	Toe tapping - Left foot (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the ten taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the tapping movements; b) mild slowing; c) amplitude	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				decrements midway in the task.	in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
LegRightOff	Numeric	Leg agility - Right leg (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications).
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowness; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing in speed; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
LegLeftOff	Numeric	Leg agility - Left leg (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				slowness; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing in speed; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ChairOff	Numeric	Arising from chair (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems. Able to arise quickly without hesitation.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Arising is slower than normal; or may need more than one attempt; or may need to move forward in the chair to arise. No need to use the arms of the chair.	
			2	Mild: Pushes self up from arms of chair without difficulty.	
			3	Moderate: Needs to push off, but tends to fall back; or may have to try more than one time using arms of chair, but can get up without help.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			4	Severe: Unable to arise without help.	
GaitOff	Numeric	Gait (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Independent walking with minor gait impairment.	
			2	Mild: Independent walking but with substantial gait impairment.	
			3	Moderate: Requires an assistance device for safe walking (walking stick, walker) but not a person.	
			4	Severe: Cannot walk at all or only with another person's assistance.	
GaitFreezingOff	Numeric	Freezing of gait (off medication)	0	Normal: No freezing.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Slight: Freezes on starting, turning or walking through doorway with a single halt during any of these events, but then continues smoothly without freezing during straight walking.	
			2	Mild: Freezes on starting, turning or walking through doorway with more than one halt during any of these activities, but continues smoothly without freezing during straight walking.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: Freezes once during straight walking.	by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Severe: Freezes multiple times during straight walking.	
StabilityOff	Numeric	Postural stability (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems: Recovers with one or two steps.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: 3-5 steps, but subject recovers unaided.	
			2	Mild: More than 5 steps, but subject recovers unaided.	
			3	Moderate: Stands safely, but with absence of postural response; falls if not caught by examiner.	
			4	Severe: Very unstable, tends to lose balance spontaneously or with just a gentle pull on the shoulders.	
PostureOff	Numeric	Posture (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their
			1	Slight: Not quite erect, but posture could be normal for older person.	
			2	Mild: Definite flexion, scoliosis or leaning to one side, but patient can correct posture to normal posture when asked to do so.	
			3	Moderate: Stooped posture, scoliosis or leaning to one side that cannot be corrected	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				volitionally to a normal posture by the patient.	medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			4	Severe: Flexion, scoliosis or leaning with extreme abnormality of posture.	
GlobalOff	Numeric	Global spontaneity of movement (off medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Slight global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			2	Mild: Mild global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			3	Moderate: Moderate global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			4	Severe: Severe global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
PostTremRightOff	Numeric	Postural tremor - Right hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
PostTremLeftOff	Numeric	Postural tremor - Left hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	
KinTremRightOff	Numeric	Kinetic tremor - Right hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
KinTremLeftOff	Numeric	Kinetic tremor - Left hand (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	
RestTremRUEOff	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – RUE (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					by the PDMedAbstain variable.
RestTremLUEOff	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – LUE (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremRLEOff	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – RLE (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					by the PDMedAbstain variable.
RestTremLLEOff	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – LLE (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremLipOff	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – Lip/jaw (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					by the PDMedAbstain variable.
RestConstOff	Numeric	Constancy of rest (off medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Slight: Tremor at rest is present ≤ 25% of the entire examination period.	
			2	Mild: Tremor at rest is present 26-50% of the entire examination period.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor at rest is present 51-75% of the entire examination period.	
			4	Severe: Tremor at rest is present > 75% of the entire examination period.	
DyskinPresentOff	Numeric	Were dyskinesias present during the exam? (off medication)	0	No	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					by the PDMedAbstain variable.
DyskinInterfereOff	Numeric	If yes, did these movements interfere with your rating? (off medication)	0	No	Clinical staff respond to this if dyskinesias were present during the exam. This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
			1	Yes	
HoehnYahrOff	Numeric	Hoehn and Yahr stage (off medication)	0	Asymptomatic.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an OFF clinical state (when a participant has a poor response in spite of taking medications). Missing values exist for participants not able to abstain from taking their
			1	Unilateral involvement only.	
			2	Bilateral involvement without impairment of balance.	
			3	Mild to moderate involvement; some postural instability but physically independent; needs assistance to recover from pull test.	
			4	Severe disability; still able to walk or stand unassisted.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			5	Wheelchair bound or bedridden unless aided.	medication before coming in for their visit, indicated by the PDMedAbstain variable.
DyskinTime	Numeric	Time spent with dyskinesias	0	Normal: No dyskinesias.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable.
			1	Slight: ≤ 25% of waking day.	
			2	Mild: 26 - 50% of waking day.	
			3	Moderate: 51 - 75% of waking day.	
			4	Severe: > 75% of waking day.	
DyskinFunc	Numeric	Functional impact of dyskinesias	0	Normal: No dyskinesias or no impact by dyskinesias on activities or social interactions.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable.
			1	Slight: Dyskinesias impact on a few activities, but the patient usually performs all activities and participates in all social interactions during dyskinetic periods.	
			2	Mild: Dyskinesias impact on many activities, but the patient usually performs all activities and participates in all social interactions during dyskinetic periods.	
			3	Moderate: Dyskinesias impact on activities to the point that the patient usually	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				does not perform some activities or does not usually participate in some social activities during dyskinetic episodes.	
			4	Severe: Dyskinesias impact on function to the point that the patient usually does not perform most activities or participate in most social interactions during dyskinetic episodes.	
OffStateTime	Numeric	Time spent in the OFF state	0	Normal: No OFF time.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable.
			1	Slight: ≤ 25% of waking day.	
			2	Mild: 26 - 50% of waking day.	
			3	Moderate: 51 - 75% of waking day.	
			4	Severe: > 75% of waking day.	
FluctFunc	Numeric	Functional impact of fluctuations	0	Normal: No fluctuations or no impact by fluctuations on performance of activities or social interactions.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable.
			1	Slight: Fluctuations impact on a few activities, but during OFF, the patient usually performs all activities and participates in all social interactions that typically occur during the ON state.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Mild: Fluctuations impact many activities, but during OFF, the patient still usually performs all activities and participates in all social interactions that typically occur during the ON state.	
			3	Moderate: Fluctuations impact on the performance of activities during OFF to the point that the patient usually does not perform some activities or participate in some social interactions that are performed during ON periods.	
			4	Severe: Fluctuations impact on function to the point that, during OFF, the patient usually does not perform most activities or participate in most social interactions that are performed during ON periods.	
FluctComp	Numeric	Complexity of motor fluctuations	0	Normal: No motor fluctuations.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their
			1	Slight: OFF times are predictable all or almost all of the time (> 75%).	
			2	Mild: OFF times are predictable most of the time (51-75%).	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: OFF times are predictable some of the time (26-50%).	Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable.
			4	Severe: OFF episodes are rarely predictable. (< 25%).	
OffStateDystonia	Numeric	Painful OFF-state dystonia	0	Normal: No dystonia OR NO OFF TIME.	This variable corresponds to Part IV (motor complications) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant. Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: ≤ 25% of time in OFF state.	
			2	Mild: 26-50% of time in OFF state.	
			3	Moderate: 51-75% of time in OFF state.	
			4	Severe: > 75% of time in OFF state.	
MedTMOOn	Numeric	Time medication was taken:	-	-	Times per 24-hour clock.
AssessTMOOn	Numeric	Time of assessment:	-	-	These variables correspond to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
SpeechOn	Numeric	Speech (on medication)	0	Normal: No speech problems.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Slight: Loss of modulation, diction or volume, but still all words easy to understand.	These variables correspond to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			2	Mild: Loss of modulation, diction, or volume, with a few words unclear, but the overall sentences easy to follow.	
			3	Moderate: Speech is difficult to understand to the point that some, but not most, sentences are poorly understood.	
			4	Severe: Most speech is difficult to understand or unintelligible.	
FacialOn	Numeric	Facial expression (on medication)	0	Normal: Normal facial expression.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Minimal masked facies manifested only by decreased frequency of blinking.	
			2	Mild: In addition to decreased eye-blink frequency, Masked facies present in the lower face as well, namely fewer movements around the mouth, such as less spontaneous smiling, but lips not parted.	
			3	Moderate: Masked facies with lips parted some of the	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				time when the mouth is at rest.	
			4	Severe: Masked facies with lips parted most of the time when the mouth is at rest.	
RigidityNeckOn	Numeric	Rigidity – Neck (on medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson’s, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of motion is achieved with effort.	
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityRUEOn	Numeric	Rigidity – RUE (on medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				motion is achieved with effort.	participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityLUEOn	Numeric	Rigidity – LUE (on medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of motion is achieved with effort.	
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityRLEOn	Numeric	Rigidity – RLE (on medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				motion is achieved with effort.	participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
RigidityLLEOn	Numeric	Rigidity – LLE (on medication)	0	Normal: No rigidity.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Rigidity only detected with activation maneuver.	
			2	Mild: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver, but full range of motion is easily achieved.	
			3	Moderate: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver; full range of motion is achieved with effort.	
			4	Severe: Rigidity detected without the activation maneuver and full range of motion not achieved.	
FingerRightOn	Numeric	Finger Tapping Right Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the 10 taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				tapping; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the 10-tap sequence.	medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during tapping or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
FingerLeftOn	Numeric	Finger Tapping Left Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the 10 taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during tapping; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the 10-tap sequence.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during tapping or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
HandRightOn	Numeric	Hand movements - Right Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st open-and-close sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
HandLeftOn	Numeric	Hand movements - Left Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) the	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				amplitude decrements starting after the 1st open-and-close sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ProRightOn	Numeric	Pronation - Supination Movements Right Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the sequence.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the sequence.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st supination-pronation sequence.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ProLeftOn	Numeric	Pronation - Supination Movements Left Hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) the amplitude decrements near the end of the sequence.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowing; c) the amplitude decrements midway in the sequence.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing c) the amplitude decrements starting after the 1st supination-pronation sequence.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ToeRightOn	Numeric	Toe tapping - Right foot (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the ten taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the tapping movements; b) mild slowing; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
ToeLeftOn	Numeric	Toe tapping - Left foot (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the tapping movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the ten taps.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the tapping movements; b) mild slowing; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the tapping movements or at	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
LegRightOn	Numeric	Leg agility - Right leg (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowness; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing in speed; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
LegLeftOn	Numeric	Leg agility - Left leg (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Any of the following: a) the regular rhythm is broken with one or two interruptions or hesitations of the movement; b) slight slowing; c) amplitude decrements near the end of the task.	
			2	Mild: Any of the following: a) 3 to 5 interruptions during the movements; b) mild slowness; c) amplitude decrements midway in the task.	
			3	Moderate: Any of the following: a) more than 5 interruptions during the movement or at least one longer arrest (freeze) in ongoing movement; b) moderate slowing in speed; c) amplitude decrements after the first tap.	
			4	Severe: Cannot or can only barely perform the task because of slowing, interruptions or decrements.	
ChairOn	Numeric	Arising from chair (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems. Able to arise quickly without hesitation.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Slight: Arising is slower than normal; or may need more than one attempt; or may need to move forward in the chair to arise. No need to use the arms of the chair.	reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			2	Mild: Pushes self up from arms of chair without difficulty.	
			3	Moderate: Needs to push off, but tends to fall back; or may have to try more than one time using arms of chair, but can get up without help.	
			4	Severe: Unable to arise without help.	
GaitOn	Numeric	Gait (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Independent walking with minor gait impairment.	
			2	Mild: Independent walking but with substantial gait impairment.	
			3	Moderate: Requires an assistance device for safe walking (walking stick, walker) but not a person.	
			4	Severe: Cannot walk at all or only with another person's assistance.	
GaitFreezingOn	Numeric	Freezing of gait (on medication)	0	Normal: No freezing.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is
			1	Slight: Freezes on starting, turning or walking through	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
				doorway with a single halt during any of these events, but then continues smoothly without freezing during straight walking.	reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			2	Mild: Freezes on starting, turning or walking through doorway with more than one halt during any of these activities, but continues smoothly without freezing during straight walking.	
			3	Moderate: Freezes once during straight walking.	
			4	Severe: Freezes multiple times during straight walking.	
StabilityOn	Numeric	Postural stability (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems: Recovers with one or two steps.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: 3-5 steps, but subject recovers unaided.	
			2	Mild: More than 5 steps, but subject recovers unaided.	
			3	Moderate: Stands safely, but with absence of postural response; falls if not caught by examiner.	
			4	Severe: Very unstable, tends to lose balance spontaneously or with just a gentle pull on the shoulders.	
PostureOn	Numeric	Posture (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			1	Slight: Not quite erect, but posture could be normal for older person.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			2	Mild: Definite flexion, scoliosis or leaning to one side, but patient can correct posture to normal posture when asked to do so.	
			3	Moderate: Stooped posture, scoliosis or leaning to one side that cannot be corrected volitionally to a normal posture by the patient.	
			4	Severe: Flexion, scoliosis or leaning with extreme abnormality of posture.	
GlobalOn	Numeric	Global spontaneity of movement (on medication)	0	Normal: No problems.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Slight global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			2	Mild: Mild global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			3	Moderate: Moderate global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
			4	Severe: Severe global slowness and poverty of spontaneous movements.	
PostTremRightOn	Numeric	Postural tremor - Right hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	
PostTremLeftOn	Numeric	Postural tremor - Left hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	
KinTremRightOn	Numeric	Kinetic tremor - Right hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
KinTremLeftOn	Numeric	Kinetic tremor - Left hand (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight: Tremor is present but less than 1 cm in amplitude.	
			2	Mild: Tremor is at least 1 but less than 3 cm in amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: Tremor is at least 3 but less than 10 cm in amplitude.	
			4	Severe: Tremor is at least 10 cm in amplitude.	
RestTremRUEOn	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – RUE (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremLUEOn	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – LUE (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremRLEOn	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – RLE (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremLLEOn	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – LLE (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestTremLipOn	Numeric	Rest tremor amplitude – Lip/jaw (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Slight.: < 1 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			2	Mild: > 1 cm but < 3 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			3	Moderate: 3 - 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
			4	Severe: > 10 cm in maximal amplitude.	
RestConstOn	Numeric	Constancy of rest (on medication)	0	Normal: No tremor.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are
			1	Slight: Tremor at rest is present ≤ 25% of the entire examination period.	
			2	Mild: Tremor at rest is present 26-50% of the entire examination period.	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
			3	Moderate: Tremor at rest is present 51-75% of the entire examination period.	receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			4	Severe: Tremor at rest is present > 75% of the entire examination period.	
DyskinPresentOn	Numeric	Were dyskinesias present during the exam? (on medication)	0	No	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Yes	
DyskinInterfereOn	Numeric	If yes, did these movements interfere with your rating? (on medication)	0	No	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their
			1	Yes	

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
					Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
HoehnYahrOn	Numeric	Hoehn and Yahr stage (on medication)	0	Asymptomatic.	This variable corresponds to Part III (motor examination) and is reported by clinical staff on behalf of a participant during an ON clinical state (when participants are receiving medication and have a good response). Missing values exist for participants not taking medication for their Parkinson's, indicated by the PDMedYN variable
			1	Unilateral involvement only.	
			2	Bilateral involvement without impairment of balance.	
			3	Mild to moderate involvement; some postural instability but physically independent; needs assistance to recover from pull test.	
			4	Severe disability; still able to walk or stand unassisted.	
			5	Wheelchair bound or bedridden unless aided.	

University of Pennsylvania Smell ID Test (UPSIT)

Table Description: University of Pennsylvania Smell ID Test

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 12 – University of Pennsylvania Smell ID Test' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
Booklet1	Numeric	Score from booklet #1:	-	-	
Booklet2	Numeric	Score from booklet #2:	-	-	
Booklet3	Numeric	Score from booklet #3:	-	-	
Booklet4	Numeric	Score from booklet #4:	-	-	

Vital Signs (VitalSigns)

Table Description: Vital Signs

View Source Instruments: Refer to the '1. Source Instruments - Case Report Forms (CRFs)' folder within the 'Clinical data.zip' file.

Details: This information was collected from all study participants during screening via the 'Form 8 – Vital Signs' CRF.

Variable Name	Data Type	Variable Description	Value	Value Description	Notes
VisitDTDays	Numeric	Date of visit: [Derived]	-	-	This variable was converted from a date to days elapsed since consent for de-identification purposes
Pulse	Numeric	Heart rate/pulse:	-	-	This variable represents heart rate in units of beats per minute
Respiratory	Numeric	Respiratory rate:	-	-	This variable represents respiratory rate in units of breaths per minute
SystolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (systolic):	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
DiastolicBP	Numeric	Blood Pressure (diastolic):	-	-	This variable represents blood pressure in units of mmHg
Temp	Numeric	Temperature measurement:	-	-	This variable represents temperature in Celsius
TempMethod	Numeric	Temperature method:	1	Oral	
			2	Axillary	
			3	Tympanic	
			4	Other	
WeightKg	Numeric	Weight:	-	-	This variable represents weight in kg
HeightCm	Numeric	Height (standing):	-	-	This variable represents height in cm

